

Under review

(Grant Agreement 101093921)

Deliverable D1.2 - Report on the methodologies and recommendations used for citizen engagement

WP1 – Mapping citizens engagement practices to improve Climate Resilience

Version 0.0.4 | December 2024

HORIZON-MISS-2021-CLIMA-02-05 - Local engagement of citizens in the co-creation of societal transformational change for climate resilience

Document History

Deliverable Title	Report on the methodologies and recommendations used for citizen engagement
Brief Description	This deliverable covers the research activities, as well as the results obtained, from analysing existing citizen engagement methodologies and conducting expert interviews, resulting into citizen engagement recommendations.
WP number	1
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Deliverable Due Date	31/12/2024
Actual Delivery Date	20/12/2024
Nature of the Deliverable	Report
Dissemination Level	Public

Date	Ver.	Contributers	Comment
08/10/2024	01	Eulàlia Baulenas	First draft
15/11/2024	02	Eulàlia Baulenas, Sam Pickard	Revised draft
29/11/24	03	Enora Bruley and Anna Scolobig	Internal review
18/12/24	04	Eulàlia Baulenas, Sam Pickard	Final deliverable

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1. Executive Summary

This report, *Deliverable D1.2: Report on Methodologies and Recommendations for Citizen Engagement*, is a key output of the adaptation AGORA project. The report addresses the need for reviewing and analysing citizen engagement practices that support climate action and a more resilient society. This report is based on the activities conducted under Task 1.2, which focuses on analysing existing methodologies, identifying best practices, and offering actionable recommendations to enhance citizen engagement initiatives (CEIs) across a diversity of contexts.

The research draws from several sources of information. On the one hand, it contains a review of existing citizen engagement guidelines and frameworks, including contributions from the European Commission (EC), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and other international organizations, as well as EU-funded projects. This was complemented by data collection activities, such as expert surveys and interviews, and interactive peer-learning workshops. These methods provided rich insights into both the success factors and challenges of citizen engagement, and helped form the basis for this report's findings and recommendations.

The findings highlight several factors for successful citizen engagement. Aspects that appeared to be important are to hold clear objectives, communication strategies tailored to the different actors part of the initiative, and paying attention to the intangibles of the process, such as the learning processes that happen for all those involved. Additionally, fostering partnerships and networks is emphasized as a means to enhance collaboration. The results also suggest that some challenges persist, particularly in engaging marginalized groups or ensuring that CEI outputs translate into meaningful policy or community actions. Nonetheless, innovative practices such as climate markets (i.e. informal conversation spaces in which citizens gather to discuss matters related to climate change), new forms of deliberative processes allowing for conflict, and the improvement of digital tools, demonstrate significant potential for fostering inclusive and impactful engagement.

The work conducted in Task 1.2 also underscores the importance of adaptability in designing CEIs to suit varying local contexts and needs. Overall, whilst this report offers actionable recommendations to strengthen CEIs, it also aims to highlight that one best practice in a given context might not work for a different one. This is because of the complexity of citizen engagement initiatives and all related factors. However, by integrating lessons learned from diverse projects and initiatives, as well as the peer-learning activities, this report provides practical guidance for policymakers, practitioners, and researchers aiming to bridge gaps in citizen engagement and climate adaptation. Ultimately, the findings may contribute, if implemented, to strengthening democratic processes, enhancing inclusivity, and promoting more sustainable and resilient outcomes in the face of climate challenges.

2. Background for WP1

Work Package 1 (WP1) aims to identify and analyse key projects and initiatives related to citizen engagement and empowerment surrounding climate change adaptation in Europe. Three tasks contribute to the fulfilment of these overall objectives (lead partner in brackets):

- **Task 1.1** Review and update existing mapping of citizen engagement initiatives related to climate adaptation in Europe [BSC]
- **Task 1.2** Analyse methodologies and practices employed to engage citizens [BSC]
- **Task 1.3** Compile and analyse capacity building resources for climate change adaptation and fighting disinformation campaigns [IBE]

This report details the work conducted under Task 1.2 to fulfil the aims of this task, which revolves around analysing methodologies and practices for citizen engagement with a focus on the field of climate change adaptation. The major output from this report is a set of recommendations that have been compiled from analysing existing methodologies and generating new insight from surveying, interviewing and carrying out interactive workshops with experts in the field.

Box 1: Task 1.2 description and expected activities, as detailed in the Grant Agreement

Review and analyse existing methodologies (M1-M24)

This task will review methodologies for citizen engagement being implemented in existing climate adaptation and citizen engagement projects. This information will be gathered using a **survey** sent to the identified projects (outcomes from Task 1.1). The survey's main goal is to identify lessons learned and detect (best) practices in terms of methodologies for citizen engagement that are currently used across these projects taking into consideration the different contexts in which they take place. An **analysis** of these methodologies will be performed with reference to a series of indicators, such as impact on the project-related climate resilience activities using the evaluation framework developed in Task 3.2. The results of the survey and the analysis will be discussed with responsible stakeholders of the identified projects. They will support the development of the evaluation framework foreseen in Task 3.2 which will be applied in Task 2.3 to evaluate and improve citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies.

The report begins with a brief introduction to the main themes related to citizen engagement practices. This is followed by the methodology implemented to design the survey and the data-collection strategy before we turn to the results from this and related tasks. These include the literature review conducted across Tasks 1.1. and 1.2, the cross-work package peer-learning workshops conducted in November 2023 and December 2024, the review of existing methodologies, and the data obtained from the expert survey and interviews.

2.1 Defining citizen engagement and the four pillars of AGORA

For the AGORA project, our focus is on how citizens can be actively empowered to influence climate change adaptation decisions. As detailed in Deliverable 1: Mapping of existing citizen engagement initiatives, we built the definition of citizen engagement based on the literature on deliberative democracy. As such, we excluded from the concept of ‘engagement’, those initiatives where citizens are mere recipients of information (e.g., one-way communication about adaptation actions). A key element of deliberative democracy is public deliberation, which we understand through Gastil’s (2000, p. 22) definition, cited by Delli Carpini et al. (2004):

“Public deliberation is discussion that involves judicious argument, critical listening, and earnest decision making. Following the writings of John Dewey, full deliberation includes a careful examination of a problem or issue, the identification of possible solutions, the establishment or reaffirmation of evaluative criteria, and the use of these criteria in identifying an optimal solution. Within a specific policy debate or in the context of an election, deliberation sometimes starts with a given set of solutions, but it always involves problem analysis, criteria specification, and evaluation.”

This definition highlights essential activities in Citizen Engagement Initiatives (CEIs), such as problem deliberation—in our case, climate change adaptation—and the identification of possible solutions through generally consensus-based discussion. These aspects are crucial for the operationalization proposed in Box 1 below, in which CEIs embody discursive participation, which emphasizes dialogue over voting-based political participation. The rise of discursive participation corresponds with the “deliberative turn” of the early 2000s (Jacobs et al., 2009) and has been further emphasized in the context of the climate crisis (Willis et al., 2022). Thus, another fundamental principle we adopt is that the process of discursive participation is as valuable as its outcomes (e.g., proposed solutions). Chambers (2003, p. 309) captures this concept as follows:

“Deliberation is debate and discussion aimed at producing reasonable, well-informed opinions in which participants are willing to revise preferences in light of discussion, new information, and claims made by fellow participants. Although consensus need not be the ultimate aim of deliberation, and participants are expected to pursue their interests, an overarching interest in the legitimacy of outcomes (understood as justification to all affected) ideally characterizes deliberation.”

Chambers’ perspective highlights five key conditions for public deliberation—universalism, inclusivity, rationality, agreement, and political efficacy (Jacobs et al., 2009, pp. 9-13). Building on these theoretical insights, we propose a practical working definition of “citizen engagement” to guide all data collection activities. This definition also establishes clear boundaries for what qualifies

as citizen engagement. We identify four essential characteristics of public deliberation that frame citizen engagement as a form of discursive participation.

Box 2: Defining a CEI

In Task 1.1 and in collaboration with other partners we sought a working definition of a CEI to use to bound our work when mapping the CEI initiatives. As we have come to present and publish our ongoing work in various forums since, we have also revised this definition for clarity and ease of understanding. Thus, following discussion and iteration, and based on the work of Chambers (2003) and aligned with the European Commission (2024) definition of citizen engagement¹, our working definition of an adaptation-relevant CEI is one that:

Must:

- Include discourse with other citizens: actions of talking, discussing, debating, and/or deliberating, expressly considering “talking” as a form of participation
- Focuses on local, national, or international issues of public concern, which for AGORA specifically refers to climate change adaptation action

Can:

- Be linked to civic and political processes
- Occur through a variety of media (not only face-to-face exchanges)

Finally, this work also relies on the research conducted in WP3, under the development of a citizen engagement evaluation framework (see Deliverable 9, based on D3.2). The framework conducted Delphi methodology to obtain the four main pillars of AGORA, considering as pillars the impacts that were expected from citizen engagement. These are:

- a) Producing relevant knowledge and action adapted to local needs
- b) Achieving just representation and participation
- c) Generating mutual learning
- d) Producing improved collaboration

For more information on the operationalisation of these pillars, which are themselves based on a series of actions, see please “Deliverable 9: Refined and updated framework to co-evaluate citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies”.

¹ “citizen engagement” refers to the involvement of citizens in participatory processes of decision making, implementation and monitoring, to improve quality, transparency and ownership of policies at local, national and EU level (12), which has been strongly supported by the Conference for the Future of Europe and the resulting European Citizens Panels for addressing current and future challenges and adapting new tools through citizens’ panels in key areas (13).” European Commission. (2024). Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/736 of 1 March 2024 on a Code of Practice on citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation. Official Journal of the European Union, L 185, 1–10

2.2 Contribution of the AGORA project to the Mission objectives

This AGORA task has contributed to the overall Mission call objectives in the following ways:

Figure 1: Contribution of the adaptation AGORA project to the Mission objectives

Objective's	Contribution
<p>[Ob. 1] Providing direct support to the regions and communities sharing relevant state-of-the-art knowledge, best practices and emerging innovations on how best to engage citizens and stakeholders and providing guidance and support regarding the implementation of citizen and stakeholders engagement activities</p>	<p>Gathering state-of-the-art knowledge on citizen engagement practices through the review of methodologies and expert interviews.</p> <p>Generating resources for citizen engagement, such as best (targeted) practices.</p>
<p>[Ob. 2] Undertaking research and testing innovative solutions using the citizens and stakeholder engagement activities ongoing in the regions and communities as case studies to better understand their success factors and to explore and experiment with new innovative ways of engaging citizens and stakeholders in transformative processes, and to feed this information back to all regions and communities</p>	<p>Review of citizen engagement initiatives related to best practices: citizen assemblies, climate markets, world cafés.</p> <p>Preparation of guidelines for the AGORA Digital Handbook.</p>
<p>[Ob. 3] Ensuring synergies between the Mission and other relevant initiatives in engaging citizens and stakeholders at local, national, and European level and to share relevant knowledge and experience made in the Mission more broadly.</p>	<p>Conducting two peer-learning workshops to exchange expertise among experts, including the members of the AGORA Consortium and citizen engagement experts.</p>

3. Methodology

Given the wealth of experience on how to conduct citizen engagement in general, including in climate adaptation settings in Europe, we have taken an approach that draws in different sources of good and bad practices. Because CEIs happen in the real world, it was also important for us to bring together different types of knowledge – including academic, institutional and practical– about how CEIs can be designed and implemented. Collecting these different types of expertise and experience necessitated distinct approaches to data gathering. Thus, the following section explains how through literature analysis, expert surveys and interviews, interactive workshops, and interlinking with work in other WPs we have brought together the data presented in the results section. We also note here that, although the structure here makes it seem linear, this has been an iterative process during which we have continued to learn more about the potential for design and implementation to impact the quality of CEI outputs and outcomes.

3.1 Review of existing methodologies

This subsection describes the activities conducted to review existing methodologies for citizen engagement. The review relied on the results obtained through the mapping of task 1.1 (see Deliverable 1.1) and added desk research to identify resources for citizen engagement available online and directed to administrations, city planners and the general public. The keywords used to identify these resources were, ‘citizen engagement’, ‘citizen participation’ AND ‘practices’, ‘methodologies’, ‘recommendations’. Many of the identified resources originate from European and international institutions, as well as EU-funded projects which revolved around citizen engagement. Some of these resources were also provided within the Mission Adaptation Europe which are those more explicitly targeting actions related to climate change adaptation. The list of reviewed methodologies, which include a range of guidelines, handbooks and booklets can be found in section 4.2.

To proceed with the review of these documents, we conducted a two-step approach. First, we reviewed each of the documents and summarised them to identify key characteristics, principles, and practices, as well as resources available in each. In a second step, each guideline was systematically evaluated based on specific criteria, including actionability, inclusivity, scalability, and capacity-building measures. The criteria were obtained through a composition of top-down approach consisting of expert assessment based on the lessons learnt from the work conducted under WP1, both T1.1 (citizen engagement initiatives mapping) and T1.3 (capacity building resources mapping); and bottom-up approach, through the practice of grounded-theory in which the categories emerge once the analyst engages with the material and compares it, as it happened in the first step.

To ensure consistency, a coded framework was applied to quantify the presence or absence of these components across documents. This approach enables a structured comparison, and thus evaluating the strengths, limitations, and contributions of each guideline to the field of citizen

engagement. The results for the first step can be found in Appendix, and for the second step in the Results section.

3.2 Peer-learning workshops (PLWs)

Alongside the work in WP1, we were involved in the peer-learning workshops (PLWs) in WP6, organising two (PLW1 and PLW3) and participating in the other (PLW 2). These are of key relevance for the topics covered in WP1 and specifically in T1.2. These workshops are key opportunities to crowd-in knowledge from the AGORA and wider community and are essential part of data gathering (PLW1), and showcasing (PLW2) and validating (PLW3) emerging results for T1.2.

PLW1 focused on identifying practices for engagement which contributed to the four pillars of the evaluation framework (T3.2) and assessing whether the practices involving stakeholders were also applicable to citizens. This is the focus of this section.

In addition, we include summary details for the other PLWs given they are also relevant to this task and this deliverable. PLW2 was led by AGORA partners ICLEI and held at the EURESFO 2024 conference. It focused on how to design engagement activities in real-world case studies being carried out as part of the AGORA pilots and the ACCTING project. Our role was to provide background on the design of CEIs and we presented the synthesised findings from our review of the literature and PLW1. PLW3 is scheduled for December 2024 (per the Grant Agreement they should be held annually) and will be used to validate the findings presented in this deliverable.

3.2.1 Peer-learning workshop I

Stakeholder and citizen engagement: lessons learnt and steps ahead (Nov 2023 and Jan 2024)

Our initial plan was to use PLW1 as an online workshop to share experiences around citizen engagement that are held by teams within and contributing to the different WPs (see Section 3.3) and to generate a list of engagement practices relevant to the desired impacts of CEIs. However, when planning the workshop, it became clear that most of the experience within the AGORA community as well as some strands of the literature (e.g. co-production) focused on engaging stakeholders in general, rather than citizens specifically. Thus, after sharing examples from the different WPs and perspectives (Part 1), we decided to first generate a long list of stakeholder engagement practices related to AGORA's target impacts (Part 2), and to then interrogating which of these were also appropriate for engaging citizens (Part 3).

We also opted to change the original logistics when, during the first online workshop in November 2023, we realised it would be better to take more time over the discussions rather than rush the process. Thus, we decided to interrogate the relevance of stakeholder-engagement practices for engaging citizens at a separate time. Thanks to the flexibility of the AGORA community, we were able to hold this Part 3 as an in-person workshop as part of the General Assembly in Zaragoza in January 2024. We believe this change had a huge benefit for the quality of the discussion and interaction between participants, and thus for robustness of the data collected.

Part 2: Generating Stakeholder Practices

Following the general introduction to the aims of the workshop, participants were asked to divide themselves into “teams”. Teams were divided according to which specific goal of a CEI participants wanted to focus on; this aimed to avoid producing the highly generalised best practices that are common in the literature. The four goals used were the four pillars of the AGORA Evaluation Framework developed in WP3 and presented as **Deliverable 3.2**: Refined and updated framework to co-evaluate citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies.

- Team 1 - Producing relevant knowledge and action adapted to local needs
- Team 2 - Achieving just representation and participation
- Team 3 - Generating mutual learning
- Team 4 - Producing improved collaboration

Our findings from the literature review that suggested practices that can affect the outcomes of citizen engagement can be divided into activities, methods and decisions taking place in three main stages of the engagement process. To understand whether our findings for individual CEIs may be more widely applicable, we also sought to better understand how the context or purpose of the CEI may affect the practices employed and their outcomes (which we call Stage 0 in attempt to show it is outside of the CEI process; i.e. it starts, before can be impacted by the process, and will continue after). We thus intentionally divided the discussion into the following four steps (one per engagement stage) and asked each team to move through them sequentially:

- Step 0: The context and purpose of the CEI;
- Step 1: Pre-engagement (planning and preparing);
- Step 2: On-the-day engagement (how activities are carried out);
- Step 3: Post-engagement (evaluation and next steps).

1st peer-learning workshop

Part 2 - (Online) World Café - Sharing Good/Bad Practices

- Pick your team
 - Team 1 - relevant knowledge and action adapted to local needs;
 - Team 2 - achieving just representation and participation;
 - Team 3 – generating mutual learning;
 - Team 4 – producing improved collaboration.
- Go to your breakout room
- Open your team's collaborative document
- 15 minutes for each of the 4 phases
 - we will broadcast a message when it's time to change
 - plan for a short break after phase 2
- Please choose one or two volunteers to report back to the group afterwards

Figure 2: PLW1 Participant Instructions (Part 2)

Each team was asked to provide examples of good or bad practices that would likely support or hamper the realization of their team's goal at each step. A 10-15 minute discussion per step was actively facilitated by us and volunteers from other AGORA partners. We used an online whiteboard to collect good and bad practices on post-it notes. We also provided space for extra information that any of the participants wanted to add related to the practices. An example of one of the steps for one of the teams is shown in **Figure 3**.

How you can ensure all voices are being heard: going around and asking whether everyone has understood the exercise. Look at the dynamics of the discussion, ask the more quiet people to share their thoughts/ write it down.

Useful to going outside as these kind of exercises are based on experiences: going outside can also shift power balances - being outside is usually a neutral space.

Using other methods such as drawing/building with play dough or lego can also shift power balances and make exercises more interactive and break down barriers

Figure 3: Example of online whiteboard from PLW1 (Part 2, Team 1, Step 2).

To facilitate deliberation and to attempt to ensure a broad range of views and experiences with fewer than expected attendees, we decided to split the online group only among the first two teams. Thus, at the end of the first online workshop, we had suggested practices for two of the four teams and agreed that having understood the task, participants would add examples to the remaining teams' whiteboards individually/asynchronously before the second meeting. **Table 1** shows the number of inputs provided for each team/step.

Table 1: Number of good (supporting) and bad (hampering) practices gathered per team per step/stage

		Practices per goal							
		Relevant knowledge		Just representation		Mutual learning		Improved collaboration	
		Good	Bad	Good	Bad	Good	Bad	Good	Bad
Stage	Context	11	11	7	5	12	7	8	2
	Pre	8	6	20	2	9	6	5	3
	During	14	8	17	3	11	7	7	2
	Post	9	5	1	0	8	5	6	4
	Total	42	30	45	10	40	25	26	11

Source: Pickard and Baulenas (2024)

Part 3: From Engaging Stakeholder to Engaging Citizens

The second meeting was held in person with 34 people in January 2024 in Zaragoza on the sidelines of the AGORA general assembly. Having gathered a large number (229) of practices for engaging stakeholders via the online whiteboards, we planned to use our meeting in Zaragoza to convert the stakeholder-relevant practices – which we had located in different stages of the engagement process and which were generated by different teams – to citizen-relevant practices. We presented this intended outcome to the participants on the day (**Figure 4**) and emphasised our gratitude for the participants’ time and the value that each of brought to the discussions.

What will be the outcome of this exercise?

ENGAGEMENT PHASE	PRACTICE	Evaluation framework key themes			
		Relevant knowledge and action adapted to local needs	Achieving just representation and participation	Generating mutual learning	Producing improved collaboration
Context	Immersive process	✓	✓		
				
Pre-engagement				
				
During engagement	Active facilitation		✓	✓	✓
				
Pot-engagement				
				

From stakeholders to citizens workshop

House-keeping

Everyone: THANK YOU FOR BEING HERE!

We are very excited to see what comes out of this in person workshop, and how it inspires us for the year ahead :-). We consider everyone a participant, even people with double identities (M+N-T), and hopefully it is a safe space where we all feel welcomed to share our insights.

Some

guidelines:

- **Moderators (M):** your role is to prompt the group, keep them aligned to the team goal (not others) and make sure they are considering the step in question
- **Note-takers (N-T):** the group will most surely fill in the post-its themselves, but if not, please make sure that all the ideas that are said are captured before the group moves one.

Figure 4: PLW1 Participant Instructions (Part 3)

However, when we were synthesising the results from the online whiteboards used in PLW1 Part 2 to prepare for Part 3, we realised that there was considerable repetition and – in our opinion at least – many practices that would be better located in other goals or engagement stages. We did not want to simply rewrite the views of others, so instead decided to add a further step to Part 3 and begin the in-person meeting with a sorting exercise.

The group was again divided into teams reflecting the project's four goals. This time, we purposively mixed participants from different parts of the AGORA project and different partner institutions within the teams. Each team was given a hard copy of the practices that were suggested for each stage of the engagement process for their goal. The practices were printed on removable cards that were lightly stuck onto boards. Each team was then asked to carry out three steps.

Table 2: PLW1 Participant instructions (Part 3, Step 1 to Step 3) - from stakeholders to citizens

Description	Slides
<p>Step 1: Each team had to decide whether each practice was most closely related to their team’s goal, or if it would be better suited in another team. At the end of this round, practices deemed more applicable to another team’s goal were passed to that team. In general, this was straightforward, but in a few cases practices circulated between the teams, suggesting they may be relevant to more than one goal.</p>	<p>From stakeholders to citizens workshop Step 1 – Exchanging with other teams</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Look at all of the suggested practices • Do you (as a team) think they should be the concern of another team? • 5 minutes to discuss • 5 minutes to pass them over
<p>Step 2: Teams were then asked to identify the most appropriate stage of the engagement process for each of the practices (both those they had kept and those that they had been given by other teams), collating those that seemed similar and/or repetitions. This generated our second version of stakeholder-engagement practices.</p>	<p>From stakeholders to citizens workshop Step 2 – Rearranging among the steps</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Look at all of the suggested practices (including the new ones) • Do you (as a team) think any should be in a different step? • 5 minutes to discuss • 5 minutes to rearrange your board
<p>Step 3: Teams were asked to consider the relevance of each stakeholder-engagement practice for engaging with citizens. A practice could be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • directly relevant; in which case teams ticked the box. • relevant with modifications; in which case teams wrote on the card the required modifications. • not relevant; in which case teams put a cross in the box. 	<p>From stakeholders to citizens workshop Step 3 – Adapting stakeholder practices for citizens</p> <p>How does what we have learned about stakeholder engagement relate to engaging citizens?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are there practices that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • are directly relevant to both stakeholder and citizen engagement? • need modifying to be used for citizen engagement? • are not relevant to citizen engagement? • Is there anything we haven't considered in our conversations so far about stakeholders that is particularly important for engaging citizens? <p>From stakeholders to citizens workshop Step 3 – Adapting stakeholder practices for citizens</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For each step (context / preparation / on-the-day / post) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ How does/could each practice relate to citizens? ○ Is there anything that is missing? • 5 minutes to discuss each step (buzzer will sound) (4 x 5 mins = 20 mins total) <p>The table in the slide thumbnail is titled 'Table 1: Modifying relevant knowledge and action adapted to local needs'. It has two columns: 'Relevant only for this' and 'Adapted to citizens'. The rows are: 'Identifying key target groups, especially paying attention to those who are traditionally underrepresented or known to be vulnerable', 'Implementing the process and objectives in the local context', and 'In situ preparation'. A legend indicates: 'Can be moved around' (arrow), 'The practice applies' (checkmark), 'Does not apply' (cross), and 'Space to adapt the practice' (pencil).</p>

Analysis and synthesis of results

The first peer-learning workshop generated a version of good and bad citizen engagement practices that can be carried out at different steps of the engagement process to support or hinder the realisation of the four key pillars of what is an “effective” CEI for the AGORA project. Most stakeholder-focused practices were considered directly transferable to engaging citizens. However, in some cases, respondents emphasized the need to consider citizens as a unique group (i.e. to tailor even more specifically to citizens’ needs and capacities).

Following the workshop, we edited the responses to streamline the suggested guidelines, recognizing that good and bad practices often “spoke” to each other (i.e. good practices were often the opposite versions of bad practices). Here, we thought it was more useful to focus on positive framings and so aside from light editing the only change we made was to invert the unhelpful practices (e.g. by replacing “a lack of resources” with “sufficient resources”). These were then edited for clarity. We did not move cards outside of their designated team/stage, but we collated practices that mentioned similar themes. This revised version of the good practices for the four pillars of CEIs in the AGORA project is presented in Table S1 (Supplementary Information). Despite our efforts, many of the practices and groups retained considerable repetition. Thus, we synthesised these practices further to produce the summary of good practices shown in Section 4 Results. This was also provided to participants in PLW2.

Some photos from the in-person part of the workshop (Part 3) are shown below.

Figure 5: Photos taken during PLW1 (Part 3, Step 3)

3.3 Expert Input: Survey and Interviews

3.3.1 Developing the framework for the survey and interviews

We dedicated considerable time and effort to designing our framework for eliciting expert input. This has changed as our own knowledge related to CEIs has evolved, benefitted from several rounds of comment from AGORA and BSC peers (see [Section 3.2](#)), and the experiences in PLW1 detailed above. Throughout the iterations, one of the key guiding principles was to seek responses that permitted tracing what practices worked well to achieve what ends under different contexts, i.e., while we were interested in good or bad practices in general, we saw the particular value in extending the work begun in the PLW1 of trying to identify practices that supported specific goals.

Box 3: Peer Review

The survey and interview framework that we launched in January 2024 was revised following a series of reviews from internal and external experts.

Internal BSC discussions

The BSC team working on WP1 is part of the Knowledge Integration Team (KIT) of the Earth Systems Services Research Group (ESS). We introduce this fact because our non-AGORA KIT/ESS colleagues possess

expertise on conducting engagement activities and have provided extensive reviews of drafts and helpful discussions as we have developed the survey. In particular, we are grateful to:

- Dr. Dragana Bojovic (Social Sciences and Humanities Team Lead and a recognised expert in co-production of climate services; Spain), and
- Dr. Asun Lera St. Clair (Senior Principal Scientist at DNV, Senior Advisor at BSC-KIT, former IPCC WGII Lead Author, and Adviser to the 2022 Spanish Citizen Climate Assembly; Spain, Norway).

External expert validation

The last step to prepare for the launch of the survey was expert validation in December 2023. Through online interviews we explained the aims of the survey, probed whether the survey questions were likely to satisfy our research aims, and sought to understand if the language used was easily understood. Three experts validated the survey:

- Dr. Ida Wallin: expert on participatory forest and environmental governance, knowledge practices, media communication and transdisciplinary research (Sweden)
- Professor Dr. Agnes Delange: Département d'Études Hispaniques et Latino Américaines, Aix-Marseille University, engaged in several Citizen Assemblies across Europe and advisor to KNOCA (France)
- Dr. Rafael Jiménez-Aybar: Environmental Democracy Adviser – Technical Advisory Unit (TAU) of the Westminster Foundation for Democracy (WFD), responsible for projects related to participatory democracy (UK, Spain)

The work documented above generated a framework for ‘when to intervene’ across the stages of citizen engagement and understanding of context and purpose introduced above. In the next sections we describe these sequential aspects more extensively.

When to intervene

We sought to identify not only what practices are important, but when they can/should be implemented. As mentioned in the previous sector, for PLW1 we divided the discussion of good practices according to four separate stages in the engagement process. Following this, during a brainstorming session (**Figure 6**) we purposively also divided the survey into the same four stages, as explained in more detail in **Table 3**.

Figure 6: Brain-storming the survey/interview framework

Table 3: Framework for when to intervene

Stage	Description	Example practices / aspects to consider
Context and purpose	The context in which a CEI occurs and the purpose of carrying it out appear to be important mediating factors both for the choice of overall CEI methodology and on the degree of success that is achieved. This is likely to be exploratory given that comprehensively defining contextual aspects of importance is challenging given the variety of CEIs carried out for such a wide diversity of purposes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General location and scale considerations • Climate change adaptation field the initiative revolves around <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ what led to a (type of) CEI being implemented (e.g. legal requirements, prior experience, available resources, or being part of a research project) ○ the motivations of the organisers/funders/implementers (e.g. just representation, better policy outcomes, improved sense of democracy), ○ the CEI’s specific objectives (e.g. creating awareness about a climate hazard, generating new knowledge, designing a sector plan, carrying out participatory budgeting).

<p>Pre-engagement</p>	<p>The adequacy of practices in this preparatory phase is an important and often overlooked aspect of CEI design. Nonetheless, pre-engagement decisions are a key determinant of the effectiveness with which the target group is reached; who constitutes that target group is a clear marker for just representation; and the objectives of the CEI can indicate the degree of citizen empowerment.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the sampling strategy, or the identification and targeting of the target population, (e.g., the general population, the elderly, the young, the vulnerable), • the communication strategy used to attract the target population to participate in the on-the-day activities (e.g. the channels or language used) • involvement in the preparation or planning for the engagement
<p>On the day</p>	<p>This comprises the meeting(s) where citizens are involved in discursive and dialogic practices and is particularly relevant to determining the extent of effective participation.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the deliberative techniques, methods, and processes used • activities to equalise the level of relevant knowledge among participants, • choices over whether to employ trained facilitators • logistical and accessibility aspects (e.g., the venue, the time/day, whether childcare or compensation are provided).
<p>Post-engagement</p>	<p>What happens after the on-the-day activities have concluded is important to ensure that citizens maintain a link to the CEI and the outputs it generates, and to interrogate whether the CEI achieved its goals and motivations.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mapping out next steps how the decisions taking during the CEI were used • conducting and communicating evaluations of the process, outputs and wider effects

Who is responsible

Cutting across the stages in the table above, where responsibility lies for decision making appears an important determinant of the extent to which different factors contribute to the “success” of a CEI. For example, who decides on the topics for background material and who presents could be key, demonstrating that preconceptions over whose knowledge is more important can manifest during citizen engagement initiatives.

Guiding respondents and adopting a general question format

When designing the survey, it quickly became clear that we were trying to ask deep questions about CEI design, practice and evaluation, and that we were trying to cover a broad set of themes. To guide respondents, we added a brief description of our intention for each question set at the top of the page and, where appropriate (i.e. where it was unlikely to bias the responses), examples.

We were keen to limit the mental load for recipients. Thus, for questions that sought similar insights, we tried to produce a generic question format. Essentially, for each motivation (aim) of the CEI, we asked the following four questions:

- What was done during the CEI in support of this motivation?
- Who was responsible?
- What was the outcome?
- What could be done differently?

We also adopted a similar structure for the question on identifying and inviting the target group, and for the question evaluating the CEI.

Closing matter / links to other aspects of AGORA

As is hopefully clear by now, this data gathering stage was carried out in tandem with several other ongoing initiatives, some related to this task, some related to the previous task in WP1, and some related to work across AGORA more broadly. It was important to make use of this opportunity to publicise these in case they were of interest to the respondents; thus, the survey concluded with:

- Next steps for this piece of work (including whether respondents would be interested in joining a results-validation workshop (PLW3))
- Details of the CEI mapping tool developed in T1.1, in case respondents wish to submit other CEIs to the database, and
- Links to wider AGORA dissemination activities, such as signing up to the AGORA newsletter or subscribing to the future Digital AGORA and Digital Academies platforms.

In total, the survey contained 28 questions. When we piloted the survey using example CEIs we had found details for in T1.1, it took around 35-40 minutes to complete.

Survey structure and navigation

We constructed a survey based on the analysis framework and also used the survey as an interview guide. The aim was to give flexibility to experts to answer in their most preferred format. We built our survey using the SurveyMonkey platform.

The questions were broadly structured according to the stages in **Figure 6/Table 3**, with an extra page before and after to gather general information. As such, most of the questions were open-ended. Throughout the different stages, we used the “piping” function to help maintain focus on the causal links between practices and outcomes (piping allows you to collect an answer and repeat it within questions later in the survey). Thus, we were able to ask about the three main motivations

for carrying out the CEI, and then ask specifically what was done to satisfy these motivations (and the degree to which they were successful). An example of the piping is shown in **Figure 7**. Here, “Equal Voice” was added as a motivation for the initiative.

Citizen engagement initiatives: practices for purposeful design

Engagement (Section 3)

In this section we seek to understand in as much detail as possible how the actions carried out within the CEI contributed to the motivations identified in Section 1 and the degree to which citizens were able to influence the process. This is the main focus of our analysis, and so we would appreciate it if you could provide **as much detail as possible** for each of the following.

18. Recalling the **first motivation** you identified in Q11 (**Equal voice**), can you provide details on:

What was done during the CEI in support of this motivation (e.g...was any background material provided, what engagement method(s) was chosen, were participants compensated for their time or was childcare available)?

Who was responsible for what?

Overall, how well was the motivation achieved, and how effective were these methods in this?

Would you do anything different if it were necessary to do a similar exercise in the future?

Figure 7: Page 4 of the survey showing how piping was used to maintain the focus practices to achieve specific goals.

We ensured that no question was mandatory, and that respondents could go back or forward with ease. As well as presenting the opportunity to reflect and change answers for survey respondents, this allowed us to send the survey as a preliminary introduction to the themes we hoped to cover in the interviews, as interviewees to click through the survey questions if they wanted to.

A full version of the survey is available in the Appendix.

3.3.2 Data collection

The final version of the survey was launched in early 2024.

We have been building a list of possible respondents since the project began. This includes experts identified during the academic and policy literature reviews, those we have met or heard speak at related events, and those that agreed to take part in the survey when adding an initiative to the CEI mapping tool in T1.1. As the research has advanced, other possible respondents were identified via snowball sampling (i.e. asking experts to identify other experts).

In total, the list contained 65 names, from academic, practitioner, government, and knowledge network backgrounds.

We were keen to allow experts to contribute in whichever way they were most comfortable and thus offered the choice of filling out the survey or of taking part in an interview via zoom.

We sent first invitations periodically throughout 2024, following up with two reminders for those who did not respond and with more details about the survey/interview for those who did. In total, 66% of our invitations went unanswered and 4 experts replied to say they would not be taking part.

Many of those interviewed have experience that spans different parts of the “CEI ecosystem” (e.g. have carried out both small and large CEIs for public and private sector clients, have both academic and practitioner experience, or work on software development but also participate in in-person events). This makes it challenging to “map” our respondents comprehensively. Nonetheless, the word cloud below illustrates some of the key attributes held by the experts that contributed.

Figure 8: Word cloud showing relevant attributes held by our expert respondents

We were somewhat surprised that the majority of those who responded positively opted for a zoom interview rather than a survey.

Interviews were organised according to experts’ availability and hosted on Zoom. Most lasted around 45 to 60 minutes and were semi-structured, i.e., we provided the survey questions in advance as guidance for the sort of themes that we were interested in, but then we were happy to let experts explain aspects they knew best or thought were more important. We used the autocaption feature to generate a transcript of each interview (typically 35 – 40 pages, two column) and asked for supporting publications and recommendations for further experts to approach (snowballing).

For the experts that opted to fill out the survey, we reviewed the responses as they came in and if we hadn’t seen an entry, we checked back with them after a week to see if they had any challenges

or still wanted to add anything. The survey results were downloaded from the Survey Monkey platform and added to a spreadsheet for analysis. In total, we collected 21 expert interviews.

3.3.3 Data analysis

The goal of the data analysis was to identify lessons learned and detect (best) practices in terms of methodologies for citizen engagement currently used across these projects, taking into consideration the different contexts in which they take place. In a first step to analyse the interview data, we conducted content analysis through the software MAXQDA using a grounded-theory approach, by which the codes emerged as we were analysing the interviews (**Table 4**). However, as we had already conducted literature review and the several other activities related to this deliverable, such as the peer-learning workshop, the key themes that emerged also had a structure that resembled our prior structuring of the field, considering the stages of citizen engagement. Whenever possible, the codes used were taken from the vocabulary that respondents were using (e.g., “Evaluation”). For those interviews which were submitted via SurveyMonkey, we did not proceed with coding as the answers were more succinct. These answers were merged with the analysis, fitting well into the themes that had emerged.

Alongside analysing emerging themes for CEIs in general, we also reanalysed the data specifically looking for themes that aligned with the four pillars of the AGORA evaluation framework.

Table 4: Code system

Code System		#
		233
GENERAL		0
	Visibility	7
	Goal	18
	Description	3
	Status quo - perspective	6
	Evolution	14
EXPERT - POSITIONING		0
	Self-perspective re CE	10
	Positioning	8
GOVERNANCE		1
	How	1
	Leadership	2
	Flexibility	2
	Culture	6
	Knowledge managers	4
SELECTION		5
	Contributing factors	4
	Attrition	1
DESIGN		0
	Contributing factors	3
	Resources	1
	Clarity	4
	Ownership	5
	Equalising	2
	Empowerment	2
	Communication	12
	Roles	4
	Maxi public	1
	Facilitators	2
	Organisers	2

	Opposition	3
	Sponsors	5
	Citizens	3
	Experts	7
	(Dis)agreement	10
	Process	20
	Budget	4
EVALUATION		0
	Roles	1
	After	2
	During	2
OUTCOMES		1
	Attitude change	4
	On the public in general	1
	Experience	2
	In the other's shoes	5
	Network-building	4
	Representativeness	2
	Output	5
	Perspective	7
	Contributing factors	0
	Continuity	2
	Getting back	4
	Political will	4
	Value alignment	5

It is important to note that in Section 4 Results we analyse the interview responses focusing solely on the topics that emerged during those discussions rather than giving input to all the elements of the framework. This distinction is important as it highlights the primary aspects that experts considered significant when asked about citizen engagement. These topics may differ from those identified in other sources, such as the literature review or peer-learning workshops. For example, the workshops were structured around theoretical insights from the literature, aiming to gather themes across all phases of citizen engagement. In contrast, the interviews reveal only the themes that experts deemed relevant.

3.3.4 Data validation - PLW3

In December 2024 we held a further peer-learning workshop (PLW3) with experts from the AGORA project and interviewed experts. The workshop employed a participatory and interactive approach, using the Miro online whiteboard as a central collaborative tool. This digital platform facilitated real-time engagement, enabling participants to visualize ideas, co-develop concepts, and contribute to shared outputs. The methodology was designed to promote discursive participation, drawing on principles of deliberative democracy where open dialogue, critical reflection, and consensus-building were prioritized. The process was structured into a series of sessions, and relied on supporting slides in which first the content of the discussion was presented, and then the discussions moved to the Miro board. Each of the three topics presented had a clear objective and guiding instructions:

- Ice-breaker session: Where would you situate your expertise, and about which topic are you more eager to discuss about?
- Topic A: Contextual factors and enabling environment for citizen engagement

- Topic B: Knowledge transmission
- Topic C: Designing a citizen engagement initiative

The workshop agenda was designed to balance structured activities with open-ended reflection and group discussion. After the initial icebreaker to foster rapport and familiarity with the Miro functionalities, participants engaged in the thematic sessions focused on the key aspects of citizen engagement that emerged during the interviews. This methodological approach ensured that both the process and outcomes of deliberation were valued, with an emphasis on inclusivity and collaborative decision-making. The entire workshop was documented, and outputs from the Miro board are described in the next section 4. Results.

3.4 Cross-fertilisation with other work packages

All the work described under this Section benefited greatly from the cross-fertilisation activities between work-packages. Methodologies to engage citizens and stakeholders are central to various aspects of the adaptation AGORA project, as **Figure 9** shows:

Figure 9: Work conducted in AGORA related to engagement

Several meetings were organised to coordinate among the WPs and especially the tasks mentioned in the figure. Thanks to these meetings and the work conducted for the pilot projects in WP2, the AGORA team conducted the “Workshop on Citizen Engagement Methodologies for Climate Adaptation: Insights from the AGORA Project” during the ECSA 2024 conference. In turn, the workshop supported the validation of the initial results and provided further opportunities for future data gathering activities, such as the interviews.

Separate to that discussed above, a second body of literature informed the design of the expert survey. This was based on the systematic literature review of levers and barriers to co-production carried out as part of WP4 T4.1, ‘Identify enablers and barriers to co-design, co-develop and co-implement innovative solutions for climate resilience’, where 32 articles were reviewed, focusing specifically on those that addressed forms of engagement/co-production with citizens.

Another close collaboration was with WP3, where we not only contributed to T3.1 (‘Facilitate in-person Agora to identify ‘best practice’ in citizen and stakeholder engagement methodologies and co-design the Digital Agora’) but also participated in the Delphi workshop and provided feedback during the development of the evaluation framework in T3.2 (see section 2.2). The outcomes of the evaluation framework fed directly into the survey design with the four pillars given as example motivations for CEI design and other aspects used to fine tune the questions to identify which engagement practices relate to different outcomes.

Finally, combining these interactions with the work conducted under WP1, helped prepare the content for the first internal peer-learning workshop (PLW1) (24th November 2023) and its follow-up session at the General Assembly in Zaragoza (January 2024), as detailed in Section 3.2 above.

4. Results

Citizen engagement has long been in the academic spotlight and is closely linked with to debates around the practice of deliberative democracy (see Deliverable T1.1). Citizen engagement initiatives (CEIs) related to public policy decisions clearly predate those solely focusing on climate change adaptation issues. Indeed, much of the current canon is traceable to the study of citizen engagement in broader environmental concerns (e.g. the work of Sherry Arnstein in the 1960s) and attempts to innovate and revitalise democracy to counter the alienation of citizens from public decisions and the associated negative impacts on policy efficacy.

Given citizen engagement's relatively long history, our initial literature review first sought to identify existing work recommending best practices for conducting CEIs in climate adaptation. As with CEIs more broadly, much of this literature (particularly grey literature) tends to provide advice for CEIs in general. However, our work mapping adaptation-related CEIs in T1.1 has revealed a broad universe of distinct practices where generalised guidelines seem less likely to be applicable. Alongside this, few studies define a "good" or "bad" CEI, much less how specific practices can achieve positive or negative outcomes or effects. Cognizant of the large number of potential evaluation criteria being developed as part of the evaluation framework in T3.2, we refocused our literature towards seeking examples of the types of practices adaptation-related that CEIs employed (in support of the work in T1.1) and also of evaluations of CEI and practices more broadly.

Beyond these specific aspects, we also sought to use the literature review to answer overall guiding questions related to how (un)learning has occurred as CEI practices have evolved within specific communities of practice and when they were translated to new communities (e.g., their use in natural resource management, energy, and more lately climate change adaptation). Specifically, this could include:

- Which aspects of practices/norms developed, which didn't, and which factors may be responsible for these dynamics?
- How are innovations – such as new technologies like e-voting, or new approaches like mini-publics – introduced and how do they impact the practices or the outcomes?
- Is there anything specific about climate change adaptation that influences this evolution, and the factors described above?

4.1 Review of existing methodologies

The next section presents the review of existing methodologies for citizen engagement being implemented in existing climate adaptation and citizen engagement projects.

4.1.1 Existing guidelines and methodologies

The review of existing guidelines cover 10 documents either from or sponsored by European or international institutions, and which specifically target citizen engagement, or citizen engagement and participation, such as is this later the case for the Real Deal or the NEDAP guidelines. We subscribe the affirmation found in the OECD guideline, in which it is mentioned that, “many of the existing resources in the field focus on stakeholder participation. These guidelines aim to fill a void by providing practical, hands-on support to organise citizen participation processes in particular, highlighting specific considerations and providing dedicated methods with an emphasis on ensuring quality, inclusion, and impact. There are two aspects here: the fact that guidelines tend to focus more on stakeholder engagement, than citizen engagement, and the fact that some resources do not provide practical, hands-on support. In the ‘Discussion’ section, we come back to these concerns, as the work conducted under the AGORA project also aimed at addressing these two voids.

The below list indicates the methodologies reviewed. At the end of each reference, there is a keyword which indicates the field towards which is intended. The number of each resource is the reference in Table 4 below, which summarises the main aspects of each. In the Appendix 4, we provided a summary of the best practices contained in each resource.

1. European Commission. (2024). *Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/736 of 1 March 2024 on a Code of Practice on citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation*. Official Journal of the European Union, L 185, 1–10. **Keyword:** knowledge valorisation
2. MIP4ADAPT (2023). *Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Adaptation: A DIY Manual*. Manual. **Keyword:** climate change adaptation.
3. Jaubin, J. (ED.) et al. (2021). *Citizen Engagement Solution Booklet*. EU Smart Cities Information System. European Commission. 1-49. **Keyword:** city-led citizen engagement
4. Evaeus, B. (ED.) (2021). *Transforming cities together: a public engagement guide for cities*. Guide. CIVOCRACY/WWF. 1-61. **Keyword:** city-led citizen engagement
5. Stec, S., Abat, A., Hafen, F., Niestroy, I., & Sperrin, Á. (2020). *Frameworks for citizen engagement in the European Green Deal: The REAL DEAL handbook*. European Environmental Bureau (EEB). 1-84. **Keyword:** European Green Deal
6. WHO (2024). *Citizen engagement in evidence-informed policy-making: a guide to mini-publics*. Geneva: World Health Organization. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. P. 1-106. **Keyword:** mini-publics (health sector)
7. OECD (2022), *OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes*, OECD Public Governance Reviews, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/f765caf6-en> . P. 1-94. **Keyword:** capacity building for public institutions
8. Hörschelmann, K; Werner, A; Bogacki, M; Lazova, Y (2019) *Taking Action for Urban Nature: Citizen Engagement Handbook*, NATURVATION Guide. 1 – 36. **Keyword:** urban nature

9. African Union Development Agency - NEPAD. (n.d.). African Union handbook on citizen engagement. NEPAD. P. 1-56. **Keyword:** participation and engagement
10. EIT-Climate KIC (accessed October 2024). *The Climathon playbook*. EIT-Climate KIC. Online resource. **Keyword:** climathon.

Table 5 contains three categories: the first can be seen as the list of aspects which the guidelines cover and which in some way, can be representative of the keystones of citizen engagement processes. The second field is about the characteristics of the guideline. This field should not be viewed as weighted or normative, in the sense that a lack of a characteristic is pejorative, but rather as descriptive. For example, the fact that the guideline is not general implies that it gives practical steps on how an organiser could proceed to implement a given practice. The final category (resources) indicates whether the guideline contains resources related to engagement methods, citizen selection techniques, digital tools, case studies or links to further resources. The table contains three categories: 1 = Yes, the item is covered in the guideline; 0 = No, not covered; P = Partially; - = not applicable.

Table 5: Comparison of citizen engagement guidelines

1 = Yes; 0 = No; P = Partially; - = not applicable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
Citizen engagement practice – the guidelines emphasize and/or provide resources for:										
Defines objectives and expected impacts	1	P	1	1	-	P	1	-	P	1
Understanding the context	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	P
Capacity building for citizens	0	0	1	-	1	1	-	1	1	-
Capacity building for organisers	1	0	1	-	1	-	1	1	1	1
Partnership and Network-Building	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	1	1	1
Communication strategy	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	1
Incentive allocation	1	0	0	0	-	1	1	1	-	0
Monitoring and Evaluation	1	1	1	P	1	P	1	-	1	1
Characteristics										
Actionable	0	P	1	P	1	1	1	1	P	1
Principle-guided	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Scalability	-	1	1	-	1	P	1	1	1	1
Inclusivity	1	P	1	1	1	P	1	1	1	P
Continuity (vs. one-off practice)	-	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	-
Resources										
Engagement method(s) description	0	1	1	P	1	1	1	1	1	1
Target group selection methods	0	0	1	0	1	1	1	P	0	1

Digital tools (e.g. platforms)	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	P	1
Case studies	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Links to resources	0	1	1	P	1	1	1	1	1	1

The group of reviewed citizen engagement guidelines offer in most of the cases a comprehensive overview with often detailed steps on the what, why and how of citizen engagement. They often emphasize the distinction of citizen engagement relative to citizen participation, and list principles for citizen engagement as well as the reasons for opting for this practice. In this regard, the guidelines often emphasize the strengthening of democracy and social capital, improvement of policies and plans, as well as contributing to the resilience and sustainability of solutions.

In terms of the how, several guidelines emphasize the need to start with a definition of the objectives and also the expected impacts of the initiative, which means, having the end-goal in mind. They usually also mention that this step should be done together with citizens, and some mention that key definitions should also be agreed at the beginning of the process. Also, most of the reviewed guidelines include sections or steps dedicated to understanding the context. For example, the MIP4ADAPT manual and the booklet from the EC Smart Cities Marketplace booklet propose a mapping of stakeholders; whilst the former also suggests conducting an assessment of risks and vulnerabilities (it is specifically for climate change adaptation), and the latter mentions devoting efforts to understanding the culture of the place and the communities to be engaged.

Capacity building for citizens is another important keystone mentioned often in the guides, some of which even include entire sections dedicated to on how and why to perform it. The fact that these guidelines see it as an essential part of citizen engagement processes, is explicit in some of the definitions of citizen engagement, as well as implicit in the references to ‘empowerment’ of citizens or effective engagement. For instance, the OECD guidelines include this explicit mention in their definition of engagement, for which, CE is a process *“when citizens and stakeholders are given the opportunity and the necessary resources (e.g., information, data, and digital tools) to collaborate during all phases of the policy cycle and in the service design and delivery. It acknowledges equal standing for citizens in setting the agenda, proposing project or policy options and shaping the dialogue – although the responsibility for the final decision or policy formulation in many cases rests with public authorities.”*. On the other hand, some guides mention capacity building resources for organisers—and are in fact directed towards organisers—being public authorities or public institutions. However, not all of them—as indicated in **Table 5** above—provide ideas or resources on how to establish a culture of engagement or what forms of training would be required.

The guidelines also place considerable emphasis on ‘partnership and network-building’, underscoring the value of cross-sector collaboration. For instance, the Climathon handbook highlights the need to allow time for building connections throughout the event, and the code of practice from the EC proposes it to promote transdisciplinary initiatives. The NEPAD handbook

mentions how encouraging partnerships can help prioritise local knowledge, address power imbalances, and empower marginalised groups.

All except two guidelines have specific sections or reference to tailored ‘communication strategies’. This keystone should be related to the emphasis on understanding the context or conducting capacity building for both citizens and organisers, as it is seen as crucial for ensuring transparency and maintaining trust throughout engagement efforts. Although some guidelines emphasize that continued engagement should not be expected—as some participants might discontinue the process—communication is seen as key to reduce the probabilities of it. Guidelines recommend also establishing channels for regular feedback. For example, by using digital platforms or face-to-face meetings as spaces for ongoing dialogue (see the characteristic of ‘Continuity’, below). Clear communication is also emphasized to set realistic expectations, especially regarding citizens' roles and the impact of their contributions.

Despite not all guidelines explicitly mentioning it, ‘incentive allocation’ emerges as another significant component, with some guidelines proposing both financial and non-financial incentives to encourage participation and maintain engagement. In many cases, incentives go beyond immediate rewards and aim to foster intrinsic motivation by showing the long-term impact of citizen contributions. Suggestions on this later aspect range from offering formal recognition and skill-development opportunities to creating pathways for citizens to present ideas directly to decision-makers, thus reinforcing the meaningfulness of their involvement.

Finally, ‘monitoring and evaluation’ frameworks are integral to these guidelines, with most documents, such as the OECD or NEPAD handbooks, providing tools or key performance indicators (KPIs) to measure the effectiveness and impact of citizen engagement. By tracking both quantitative and qualitative metrics, such as the inclusivity of participant demographics, level of engagement, or outcomes achieved, the guidelines emphasize how monitoring may help organizers to adjust strategies and make informed improvements. Guidelines like those from the European Commission propose that monitoring should be an iterative process, adapting over time as engagement initiatives evolve. It is mentioned how this approach can help ensure accountability and solidify citizen trust in both the process and outcomes of engagement.

Characteristics

As described in Section 3 Methodology, we assessed each of the guidelines according to the following characteristics:

- Actionable: evaluates how actionable and specific the guidelines are, including step-by-step processes or tools that aid practical implementation
- Principle-guided: assesses whether the guideline is grounded in overarching principles (e.g., transparency, inclusiveness) and how well these principles are defined and integrated
- Scalability: assesses whether the guidelines are scalable for different contexts and sizes, from small communities to national or international projects

- Inclusivity: examines how well the guideline promotes inclusive practices, addresses marginalized groups, and provides tools for broad demographic engagement
- Continuity (vs. one-off practice): evaluates whether the guidelines provide practices for making citizen engagement a sustainable and continued practice, rather than a one-off exercise

Most of the guidelines are actionable, which means that they include either frameworks, methods descriptions or description of methodologies on how to conduct citizen engagement. All of them are principle-guided, as they refer to the reasons behind conducting citizen engagement. In a few cases, they also compare how certain methods, as for instance, a certain method for target group selection or the decisions on the venue, might contribute to certain principles. The scalability refers to the extent to which the guidelines may apply to different contexts and situations—from small to big budgets, from the local to the national level—and according to this assessment, it appears that as they are actionable but also general, the practices could be well adapted. The reason for this scalability appears to be two-fold: the guidelines aim to cover a range of methods with associated case studies on how they were particularly implemented, but also, it is linked to the characteristic of ‘continuity’. Continuity refers to whether the guidelines aim to establish a culture of citizen engagement, which supports the idea that several different practices could be implemented depending on the end-goal that the process aims to achieve.

Resources

Several of the guidelines stretch beyond 50 pages and contain explanations of methods with practices and examples of case studies that implemented the methods, discussions on or lists of digital tools to conduct citizen engagement, as well as links to resources. The guides cover various methods; some cover just one method, as the OECD guideline on mini-publics, and some covering a wide range. Additional methods (see Appendix 1 for explanations) mentioned in the guidelines include:

- Citizen assemblies
- Round tables
- Participatory budgeting
- Living labs
- Focus groups
- Public consultations
- Citizen science
- Workshops
- Deliberative polling
- Exposure visits/networking events
- Resource hubs
- Hackathons/climathons
- Community dialogues

- Citizen panels
- Online surveys
- Community advisory boards
- Digital platforms
- Collaborative mapping
- Salon method
- Delphi method
- Planning cells

The summary tables for each guideline (Appendix 4) include the methods covered.

4.2 Peer-learning workshop 1

The synthesised results from PLW are shown in **Table 6** (intermediate, unsynthesised results are shown in Appendix 3). Note that the pillars of the engagement framework have been edited to use more accessible language.

Table 6: Example good practices for citizen engagement (PLW 1 Synthesised Results)

Researching and preparing the ground	Planning	“On the day”	Afterwards
Making engagement relevant to the local context			
<p>Identify and seek to understand what makes the local context special and unique. Where possible, avoid generalising, and test any assumptions you make.</p> <p>Ensure that there is adequate resources (time, budget, expertise) to understand the local context.</p> <p>Immerse the organisers and all stages of the process in the local context (carry out as much in-situ as possible) and link it to locals’ topics of interest.</p> <p>Seek to tailor each stage of the engagement process to the specificities of the local context, its citizens and their needs.</p>	<p>Explicitly plan how to identify different accessibility requirements and then – ideally via a bottom-up approach – design combination of formal and informal learning methods that aim to include everyone.</p> <p>Make the effort to lay the ground for the initiative early on (i.e. in advance of the engagement process).</p> <p>Clearly define tailored evaluation/monitoring methods and secure sufficient resources (process time, money, participant capacity) to carry them out.</p>	<p>Build group activities around local case studies – e.g., real-life experiences, local data, immersive experiences like field visits – that foster a culture of actively listening to citizens to understand context- specific needs and knowledge/capacity gaps</p> <p>Set the tone for the event as one that makes participants feel like they belong to a common project by explicitly recognizing the importance of integrating different groups’ knowledge/experience together and the value of each as part of the whole</p> <p>Share criteria for evaluating/monitoring process and outputs with participants.</p>	<p>Adapt dissemination and in-person communication styles (language, delivery style, accessibility) to provide participants and other target groups’ an easily accessible summary of the material used, the information collected, the outcomes and the next steps.</p>

Making engagement fairer (accounting for power)				
<p>Conduct explicit stakeholder mapping to identify key actors (especially paying attention to those who are traditionally underrepresented or known to be vulnerable) and check the mapping comprehensively covers the target groups (i.e. avoiding gaps).</p> <p>Undertake research that engages with key stakeholders (e.g. through surveys, champions, embedded researchers) before beginning the planning process to understand vulnerabilities, socioeconomic characteristics of the target population and issues of power</p> <p>Throughout the process, tailor existing methods of working (or develop new ones) to reflect target groups' needs and to correct for power imbalances</p> <p>Throughout the process, develop purposeful communication strategies tailored to</p>	<p>Having identified key actor groups, continue preparatory research to identify barriers to engagement for these and use process design planning to break down topic complexity and address power imbalances.</p> <p>Use purposive selection (stratified for society-wide, strategic for specific target groups) to bring participants from beyond existing networks.</p> <p>Engage societal champions or impartial expert advisers to be the bridge to target groups and bring insights that then shape collaboration throughout the engagement process to accommodate different accessibility requirements and ways of working.</p> <p>Creative, open, tailored, engaging communication which helps in achieving the goals</p> <p>Ensuring adequate planning / provision of resources (process</p>	<p>Paying sufficient attention to individuals to ensure no participant's engagement is limited by their accessibility needs, e.g., logistics (appropriate timings/locations) and incidental arrangements (e.g. childcare).</p> <p>Trained facilitators effectively moderate the process, focussing on equity, diversity and inclusion to correct for power imbalances in group deliberation and decision making so that everyone (especially target citizen groups) feel comfortable to contribute.</p> <p>Sufficient resources provided to facilitate equalising communication practices; encouraging and empowering target groups and limiting "space" of powerful actors to ensure no one individual or group dominates.</p> <p>Recognising and accounting for how on-the-day representation</p>	<p>Acknowledging participants contributions, outlining how these supported the outputs, and explaining how the participants have benefitted the process and vice versa.</p> <p>Seek (anonymous) feedback from participants and establish longer-term processes that continue to empower representation in related processes.</p> <p>Communicate results of the process, outputs, next steps and evaluation in language and mechanisms that are tailored to target groups.</p>	

the target groups for the identified vulnerabilities.	time, finances, participant capacity)	may impact the deliberative outputs Explicitly recognise participants as “experts” in their field with valuable knowledge that supports the process.	
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Fostering a process of mutual learning

<p>Mapping and different levels of knowledge and capacity and desire to learn about key themes (e.g. via literature reviews, contacting those with previous local engagement experience, and exploratory meetings with local actors). Seeking to understanding what gaps need to be filled before defining the learning needs. Identifying who can teach whom what.</p>	<p>Establish the CEI as a place of mutual learning (not exchange) and provide tangible examples of what this means Creating heterogeneous work groups that are directed to consider diverse perspectives using mutual learning processes tailored to participant-identified needs Embed the process in the local culture/networks with the aim of strengthening existing links and building relationships with community members</p>	<p>Ensure communication is inclusive and relatable (e.g. provided in appropriate language(s), without jargon), and that time is provided to check inputs were accessible and has been received by participants. Openly set the expectation that participants are “experts” in their field and thus promote bottom-up approach that respects ideas and experiences (seek to “collect knowledge(s)”). Create an environment where participants actively listen to others, using creative engagement methods (e.g. role play, serious games) in a context- and power-appropriate way. Providing real-time feedback during the process to demonstrate</p>	<p>Survey, interview or otherwise seek feedback from participants and stakeholders (e.g. non-participating organisers) to evaluate and/or demonstrate what has been learned during the initiative Synthesise and clearly communicate the knowledge developed to participants and wider society (if appropriate). E.g., ask participants to proofread the outputs, checking the content and that the format is context appropriate, and aiming for the development of open-access datasets/maps/platforms</p>
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		that organisers are also attentive to the diverse views that are presented.	
Improving collaboration between societal groups			
<p>Researching prior experience with collaborative activities in the local context; what worked well, what didn't and why (e.g. are there other links/conflicts between citizens and stakeholders that facilitate/inhibit collaboration?).</p> <p>Plan tailored trust-building activities with to-be engaged citizens that use knowledge of local nuances to build on existing social capital (networks, relationships, trusted knowledge brokers etc.).</p>	<p>Set the intention for participant collaboration, ownership and communication of the process and outputs.</p> <p>Communicate clearly the goal of the process, the benefits to citizens (and other participants) of collaborating, and the opportunities to impact the outcomes. and for them to act as communicators for the initiative.</p> <p>Balance leveraging existing networks with going beyond the "usual suspects" to create a participant group that is context-specific.</p> <p>(Co-) Assess participants' competencies, expertise and capacity to contribute throughout the process and offer appropriate support to those who may need it</p>	<p>Plan and carry out activities in a way that shows commitment to supporting participants find synergies and common ground</p> <p>Collectively establish (for the facilitator to manage) clear goals and roles for each participant.</p> <p>Actively account for citizens' communication preferences and ensure material provided throughout is clear, concise and accessible for each participant who requires it.</p> <p>Provide time for formal and informal knowledge exchange among participants.</p> <p>Maintain a flexible agenda open to alternative topics, with a range of activities based on voluntary, multi-direction communication where participants recognize the value of collaborating (to them</p>	<p>Soon after the event, provide participants with feedback how the process went (e.g. recognizing the collaborations that the supported the process), a summary of the results (including how their inputs helped generate them) and opportunities to evaluate the process and outputs</p> <p>When appropriate (during the process or soon after), communicate the next steps and opportunities to stay involved or become involved in follow-on initiatives or become part of a wider engagement community (as appropriate, with consent).</p> <p>Seek to foment robust governance structures (depending on context, may be government-led or community-led) that strengthen the norm of collaborative engagement for public</p>

		and the process overall).	issues of concern while respecting participant preferences and considering social dynamics (e.g. do not force collaboration).
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4.3 Expert survey and interviews

“You opened Pandora's box”, mentioned one of the interviewed experts, providing a metaphor about what it entails to discuss about practices in citizen engagement, not in a problematic sense, but pointing out rather to the complexity of the topics and aspects involved. Citizen engagement is not a homogeneous practice, and behind the concept, there is scattered a universe of contexts, methods, practices, perspectives and positionings. As one of the experts illustrated in this sense:

“I am doing public participation for almost 15 years and can say, there might be some repeating patterns but in general no CEI is like the next; so in a very general matter, yes there are things you can apply and at the same time you will always have to decide in the single instance how to proceed.”

To make sense of the expert interview data in front of this complexity, we have divided the results into two subsections: the first analyses the answers from a generalisable perspective, whilst the second subsection makes emphasis on the need to avoid the isolation of practices and locate them within contexts and expected goals. As such, the two parts contain the following:

- I. Identification of lessons learned and detection of (best) practices in terms of methodologies for citizen engagement
- II. An analysis of these practices in reference to the core goals of Adaptation AGORA based on the Evaluation Framework for Citizen Engagement Initiatives (T3.2)

Before focusing on the praxis of citizen engagement and these lessons learnt, general or tailored, however, there were certain themes that emerged during the interviews which are described next.

4.3.1 General themes

The vision

The vision and mission of citizen engagement are about the reasons behind opting for deliberative democratic forms, relative to alternatives like representative democracy. The interviewees often referred to extrinsic factors, such as achieving more inclusive public policies, the vision of achieving a better city or as a way to fight the surge of populist movements. As intrinsic factors, to become a transformative and empowering experience for participants and a learning experience for all of

those involved. Intertwined, it is the factor that alienation and disengagement from the public sphere could be combatted, despite not being perceived as a magic bullet.

Certain forms of citizen engagement—those more related to open spaces of deliberation, rather than the more closed formats such as citizen assemblies—were seen moreover as a way to give space for society to be able to voice and express the enormous transformation that they are seeing, which will be exacerbated by climate change. Along these lines, citizen engagement is seen as an opportunity to create a “hybrid space for the collaborative and inclusive construction of desirable futures” and move policy forward when faced with political deadlocks. Moreover, some respondents pointed out the intangibles: more than the set of outputs obtained from the process, such as ideas or recommendations, the real benefits were perceived to be connecting people, building networks or bringing together citizens who, because of their milieu, might never have the opportunity to interact (see section below on ‘Outcomes’).

The perception of experts about citizen engagement is an aspect worth highlighting also under this theme. All the interviewed experts are proponents of citizen engagement, but some of them felt disillusioned and disenchanted. Despite feeling “passionate” about the topic, they had the sense that the initiatives tend to fall in a vacuum and have a poor impact on policies. The reasons mentioned were the several instances they had seen in which participants never heard back from how their recommendations were adopted (if at all) or had to wait years for a supportive government to put them into place. This was often attributed to processes being set up too vaguely from the beginning, yielding thus vague results.

The evolution

Respondents view very positively the evolution towards citizen engagement becoming more predominant in the last years. One respondent mentioned that in the late 2000s, it was still very difficult to convince public authorities to implement participatory processes. Part of this paradigm shift emerged from social movements, such as in the case of Spain with the indignados movement around 2011-2013, or the increasing role of social media in the public sphere such as in the Arab Spring (“What if these tools were designed to trigger engagement instead of polarisation?”). Amongst positive trends, respondents saw how whereas at the beginning it was more often the case that such a process was put in place to gain legitimacy for certain actions, they see it as less often the case. However, respondents also see the political influence and they believe that trends towards more citizen engagement could slowdown depending on the positioning of political representatives. Currently, there is a competitive market in place, with 100 million from the EC distributed for this type of initiatives. Some respondents mentioned this as a negative trend, having the feeling that they were “selling democracy”. About some aspects that could actively be changed, would be that the academic and practitioners’ fields are perceived to be separate, but that the paradigm overall would benefit from them joining forces. In fact, some of the respondents did mention projects in which both worlds were part of the processes they had seen.

However, this trend towards more citizen engagement is not perceived to be homogeneous. A respondent observed from the research they were conducting, how in Central and Eastern Europe the use of CE is lower than in other parts, and at the regional level almost non-existent, adding how “from the public authorities interviewed they found the concept even bizarre”. The respondent also mentioned how Scandinavian countries started earlier with consensus conferences, followed by the BeNeLux nations, and that it took a bit more time to reach out southern/mediterranean Europe, but currently it is also happening there. The implications are well illustrated in this quote: “It is difficult to integrate participation into a policy paradigm, as it is just not part of their world.”, and thus, the reigning policy paradigm in a given context should be accounted for when aiming at introducing deliberative practices.

The particularities of climate change (adaptation)

Citizen engagement is prevalent in plenitude of sectors, and it has arrived at the doors of topics concerned with climate change adaptation. However, there are certain particularities that emerged in the interviews relevant to implement meaningful initiatives in this field. For instance, the aspect of inclusiveness, which is intrinsic to climate justice. According to one respondent:

“This is one of the things that practitioners struggle with the most - how to become inclusive. Because it is a well-known study: either the usual suspects participate in public policy or start initiatives themselves (white, highly education, good background, better neighbourhoods). When you have a focus on climate change adaptation it becomes problematic, because it is always the less educated, less affluent, women, marginalised communities, those more affected by climate change.”

This has several implications for the design of processes: how to target those most affected by climate change, and how to design initiatives that they can both feel comfortable participating and, once they do, effectively participate. This is covered in the next subsection.

The second particularity of climate change (adaptation) is that it is not a neutral topic. And this is the case in several ways. On the one hand, there exists denialism among the population and climate misinformation is another factor that intervenes in making this a highly contested topic. On the other hand, it is experienced differently by people. As one of the respondents mentioned, “Climate change is not an abstract concept, it is part of everyday life (...). what it means for people, what it is really lost, what it has to be regained. We have to listen to the different narratives of change”. The aspect of bringing climate change closer to people’s life, is also something that the design of a citizen engagement initiative has a lot of influence upon, as it is about the stories we tell (see section ‘Framing’ below).

Finally, proposed solutions might not reach consensus as they might impact the lifestyles and praxis of large parts of the population. Whereas the praxis of citizen engagement was based on consensus-

building-, some of the experts raised the concern of whether this was desirable in all of the contexts, and in particular when dealing with aspects related to climate change.

The implications of the aspects that are covered in these themes, will be returned to in the next sections that specifically cover the aspects related to design.

4.3.2 Part I: Identification of lessons learned and detection of (best) practices

This section enters into the detection of practices for designing citizen engagement initiatives, covering all stages of the process. The topics covered are those of the actors involved, selection process for citizens, design of the engagement process (“on-the-day activities”), communication, framing and governance.

Actors

During the interviews several actors emerged as relevant, some even unexpected and that are not covered in the methodologies reviewed, or in very few. Besides the initiators, which sometimes are distinguished from the organisers (often consultancies or academic institutions part of EU-funded projects), there are also the facilitators. In small local processes, these figures may overlap, but during the interviews the issue of overlapping roles, and the challenges and advantages this may imply, did not emerge. Sponsors are figures which support the process financially or in-kind, by for instance, being champion proponents and reaching out to the own network to encourage people to participate. Topic experts, understood in wide terms, are those actors who bring in the expertise about the topic of debate during the interviews, and can play advisory roles or acting as surveillance body to monitor that the process is legitimate. Finally, three of the roles that appeared in the interviews as important but heterogeneous are those of the media, opposition and the maxi public, i.e., citizens who are not part of the process.

In **Table 7**, we gather the practices obtained during the interviews in reference to these roles and actors. The column ‘closed’ means those practices that are highly recommended to be present or implemented. The column ‘open’ is that the degree or way in which the practice is implemented, should be dependent on the context, goals and observed needs. The details about practices relative to each actor are commented within the analysis of the other themes (e.g., communication strategy, engagement design, etc.).

Table 7: Overview of actors and associated best practices

Actor	Closed	Open
Initiators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Be clear on why CE is needed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The type of process needed
Organisers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Being open to feedback and flexible to adapt the process to observed needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Format of the CE Space
Facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Have expertise Know of conflict management and multicultural settings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consensual vs. conflict-allowing practices

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Allowing for feedback • Only them responsible for moderation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The number of facilitators (although several, recommended)
Sponsors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoiding sponsors if conflict of interest can be present. Their presence can alienate part of the participants if they don't share the values of the sponsor. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In-kind sponsorship: partnering with representatives of the target groups, such as youth groups or, in an example, an activist who had a wide network, to reach out to potential participants
Topic experts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banning self-interest-guided perspectives • Receiving briefing/training for communicating accessibly 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Form of knowledge: academic, practical, experiential • Whether they just present a topic or are also present during the debating phase
Advisory		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presence of an advisory board to monitor and evaluate the process independently
Opposition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opposition to the process should be considered as a stakeholder group, to design appropriate communication strategies and off-set their impact on the process 	
Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have them on board as they can backfire the process if siding against, or support it if people know about the process and might be more willing to participate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The extent to which they will cover the process, as they can influence it
Maxi public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to be taken into account, as they might impact the process and the process might impact them 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The degree to which they are involved in the process

The interviewees mentioned the importance of having close contact between initiators (administration or the local government) and organisers (the consultancy or team that will be implementing the process). In terms of experts, that not only topic experts could be present, but also experts on the regulatory context or those who could contribute also to the design of the engagement process.

Selection process for citizens

The selection techniques covered in the interviews ranged from open calls to the random selection seen in citizen assemblies. Random selection takes a representative sample of the population, and it avoids that not only the usual suspects participate in such processes. However, some respondents indicated that additional measures need to be put in place for effective participation, as not all

subjects will have the same skills, such as rhetoric or confidence. Additionally, and specifically discussing about the particularities of climate-related aspects, one interviewee said, “It is difficult to convince people with very specific backgrounds, although it’s doable. What is even more complicated is to bring in diversity in terms of political interest and attitudes with respect to the topic. 80% politically interested, a bit critical about the topic but not radically critical about democracy. Then you get those that are holding the more mainstream attitude on climate.”. This has the implication for the selection and the engagement process. For selection, the suggestion for random selection is to add in pre-selection criteria that refer to the attitudes towards the climate, with the following caveat: “At the same time, political views should be formed during the assembly. So, making stratification based on attitudes does not totally make sense; but it could backfire.”

However, random selection might be discouraged if there is no access to the public registry, as this would imply an additional burden for the budget depending on the scale in which the initiative is conducted.

On the hand of the engagement, it implies taking decisions on whether to design a process in which consensus is sought, or rather better seen by respondents, allowing for discern among participants. Also, to provide a diversity of means by which information is transmitted: “The problem they usually have is that citizens are very different, fast-slow learners, visual to written material. The question is to provide them a variety of means that citizens can use that take into account the different backgrounds”. Also, a factor that contributes to diminishing the impact of differences amongst participants is moderation.

For open calls, and specifically if aiming at reaching a certain target and marginalised groups, a respondent indicated practices that could support -despite the difficulties-, in reaching them out. The respondent observed, “But these are the people that feel estranged, don’t trust the government, and even if the civil servants try to reach them, they don’t join. (...) Here the best practice is to go through the social security offices from the neighbourhoods. Also go with representatives of these communities.”. Lack of trust and differences in values are seen as challenges for people participating. Decisions on the place in which the citizen engagement happens are here also important, probably implicating moving away from city halls and going to the associations.

Another example of what efforts can be exerted to move away from usual suspects without using random selection, is the one illustrated in this excerpt of an interview:

“Several mayors are very interested in this concept as they suffer that it is always the same people, and the network is centuries old. The water society is deeply embedded in society, and they are powerful. Mostly male. People who can manipulate the networks. Randomly choosing citizens it is a relief they said to break the routinised networks. (..) He [a collaborator] just didn’t stop calling people and doing that work to make it feel relevant to the people. He came from

religion studies, and he got all religion organisations on board. And he just kept going. They reached a point with a critical mass, then it became easier. Actually, getting the firefighters in, is when the event was started to be perceived as serious because they were saying that it was very relevant to their work, as they deal with flooding. A lot of personal contacts, one organisation at a time, lots of calls. Slowly bringing the organisation in, and then small balling. We created an advisory board with a couple of them.”

For open calls to be successful, some respondents reached out to youth groups to promote the open call, also, or partnered with activists that had a wide network.

A question that remained open, nonetheless, it was how to reach the ‘many’. A respondent indicated how, “there's just too many people out there who just have not done it. I mean, I think as soon as you have done it yourself, you realise how powerful these tools can be.”. However, for processes that at maximum engage with a couple of hundred citizens -in populations of thousands and millions-, how to make the maxi public participant of the experience is still seen as one of the challenges of citizen engagement.

Aspects related to the engagement process design, will later determine whether the citizens that got initially engaged, maintain their presence throughout the process.

Design of the engagement process

The design refers to the decisions surrounding the engagement process. In several responses, it emerged that it should be kept flexible, and open to be changed “according to real needs”. The importance of fun was mentioned, as was allowing time at the beginning for people to really get to know each other. These findings, developed further below, suggest that the elements that promote successful engagement include inclusiveness, communication and flexibility align with the findings from WP4 efforts to understand enablers and barriers the co-production of climate solutions (see **Deliverable 4.1**: Enablers and barriers to co-design, co-develop and co-implement solutions for climate resilience).

In general, the factors that emerged as positively contributing were those of having clarity on the aims of the process, generating ownership among organisers and participants of the end-result, and equalising and empowering participants. Without clarity as a building block, the design was perceived to be a set of empty boxes with vague questions that yielded blurry results. Ownership allows for people committing to the process, but also, to support the adoption of the outputs obtained. Equalising has been dealt with in the previous subsection, but implies giving everyone equal opportunity to participate through several means, including incentives. Finally, empowerment is giving the opportunity to feel that your contributions are heard and matter, but also, the feeling of learning something by participating in the process. Whilst empowerment is covered in the post-engagement section (see below), it also emerged as part of the design process due to this linkages to the “on-the-day” engagement.

Some interviewees referenced the process, primarily for citizen assemblies, as comprising information, deliberation, and landing phases. Among these, deliberation and landing were noted as having evolved the most due to accumulated learning. Regarding information, it was mentioned that this phase should blend with deliberation, “because this latter can bring more questions and needs for information, so experts or people that can help the citizens need to join the deliberation phase too.” In the deliberation phase, experts emphasized the importance of categorizing ideas and conducting exercises that help discussions reach conclusions (“If you have 1 day it’s not enough; if you have 3 days it’s still not enough; 6 days, not enough. There is never enough time for deliberation”). A “referendum process” was highlighted, wherein respondents rank preferences on a scale of five levels multiple times to track shifts in positions. This method, while moving away from consensus-based approaches, was preferred by some respondents, provided group sizes remained small². Notably, some experts observed that participants often required more initial guidance and opted to use scenarios or “stories” with future visions.

An addition to the deliberation process was to create a networking space where initiatives could present projects, fostering further discussion and inspiration. Experts noted that when well-facilitated, such spaces fostered rapid collaboration and trust-building. During the deliberation phase, decisions were made about the degree of consensus or conflict allowed. For climate change topics, one respondent saw no need to force consensus, noting that climathons, for instance, are often structured around competition. Experienced experts also advocated for moving away from purely consensus-based deliberation, allowing room for disagreements. However, allowing too much conflict could lead to silos or coalitions, which could undermine the process. As one expert put it, “If we want to be resilient, we need to understand each other and see what each brings to the table.” High-conflict topics were sometimes avoided, especially by public authorities seeking to normalize citizen engagement, who often started with manageable issues. Ultimately, finding “the right balance” was deemed essential.

This account exemplifies one respondent's observations:

“The biggest strength of citizen assemblies is you present them with a clear task and this task involves some type of conflict or polarized question and citizens are in all the spectrum. Then citizens come together with different backgrounds, opinions, positions, and in these deliberations, they are confronted with the experiences of other people with other walks of life...They have 80-90% of

² Another reference of how this was conducted was the following: “After the group-building phase, then the process comes and we open the floor and everyone can talk and collect thoughts/wishes/concerns, everyone has a chance to speak their mind on the topic - they (experts/facilitators) open the space for inputs and they try to structure them and give them certain priorities. E.g., now we have 20 issues, let’s find 5 important ones. This creates an agenda of what they want to work on during the process. It provides ownership, and it avoids topics that they are not really concerned about.”

consensus normally in the room. And this only happens if citizens have heard what the other participants in the room have to say.”

Regarding the landing phase, this step was previously termed “recommendations.” However, after seeing that recommendations were often minimally implemented by public authorities, experts preferred to leave the outcome open. They noted that recommendations were often too numerous, leading to limited action. Shifting away from recommendations to alternatives, such as directives, could impact the deliberation phase: “Shifting away from recommendations won’t change the information part (or only a little bit) but it will change the deliberation part, especially what happens at the end of the deliberation process.”

Finally, the topic of process evaluation emerged but was less prominent. An interviewee recommended evaluating with all stakeholders, suggesting “a certain canvas approach to really identify what went well and what can be improved.” An expert commented that in a particular set of events, the facilitators stayed at the end of the day with some of the participants -sometimes going for some food-, to discuss how it had been perceived to afterwards be able to implement the feedback. In addition to evaluation, monitoring was conducted in some cases, with annual surveys to assess participant perspectives and longer-term follow-up to measure impacts. Results showed initial enthusiasm among participants but growing despondency over time due to perceived inaction in policy.

Communication

The communication was also an important aspect that emerged during the interviews. It encompasses the strategies put in place during all the process, including pre and post stages, and for all the actors involved in citizen engagement, as listed above. This includes the participants, but also the communication with the media, the maxi public, opponents and advisors. Storytelling and the imaginaries used during the process are seen as key factors in citizen engagement, and moreover in relation to climate change (adaptation).

From the beginning, the communication strategy needs to be defined with the end goal in mind. The experts mentioned how it will change depending on whether the process will yield recommendations or another type of output, such as directives (aka. the principles that should influence a given policy, rather what to do specifically). This allows for tempering the expectations of the process for participants, but also of the experts who are giving up their time (generally on weekends) and should also be included in knowing the impact that their participation might have. Additionally, to what the process will yield, and how organisers plan to come back to the outcomes, providing information about the length of the process after its end, was also considered important. For example, in the social housing project, it was mentioned how, “The length of the process was decided by the construction process (so there was a big gap between the end of the participation and the opening of the building) but participants knew this from the beginning, and it went as planned.”. Finally, experts also mentioned as important that the communication finds ways of

appealing to the public before the process starts, and find arguments that make people interested in it, independently of whether they will be part of the process or not.

The communication strategy should also account for the opponents, and the interviewees considered that if they were targeted with the communication material, it could help calm the opposition towards the process. The information they receive should involve details about the process, the project, who is behind it and for which reasons, as well as finding the aspects they care -and worry- about, and be able to respond to that.

The format of the communication also was important: on the one side, and as mentioned above, communication material should be adapted to the needs of the participants, and this may imply that different materials need to be designed. Also, the organisers and facilitators can play with the format, from more text-oriented sources to more visual formats, and providing a mix of these. For instance, from the experience conducting a World Cafe style, an interviewee mentioned how they had “two different tables with different technical people at each who had information about the design, with printouts, mood boards with images for getting inspiration, also different materials to create ideas.”

In terms of outer communication with the maxi public, some experts proposed to have a website following the process and which the ideas of participants could receive feedback from “society”. Also, another suggestion was to “propose interviews of citizens on TV (...) people see that they can identify with them because basically they look like them; they talk like their neighbour, and not like politicians. Then you might reach groups that are difficult to reach (lower educated, minority).”. One expert that had been studying the maxi public mentioned that the attitudes towards the citizen engagement process were not homogeneous. The profiles have two main axes: the attitude towards citizen engagement and towards partisan politics. Having in mind how these different profiles may react to the communication campaign, can support its design. For instance, the initiator matters for people who still care about partisan politics, and might adopt the same position.

Finally, communication is also a matter of finding the balance between not having a too isolated process, but at the same time not allowing for undesirable influences to have a place on it.

Outcomes

The outcomes of citizen engagement extend well beyond the individual initiatives. These assemblies are seen as platforms for sharing relevant knowledge and climate-related experiences. For ambivalent participants, taking part in initiatives like climate assemblies increased openness to climate issues, with some respondents noting that participants’ climate-related anxiety decreased—not because they saw the issue as smaller, but because they saw a wider range of solutions. The impact of citizen assemblies on the maxi public attitudes is also under study, with results still forthcoming. Overall, many of the experts found that including youth led to more innovative solutions and a departure from the status quo. They were seen to be much more open for new

perspectives, less cynical, have less barriers and being less politically influenced. Generally, citizen assemblies were described as consistently producing progressive outcomes.

Another frequent theme was the ability to empathize and “put oneself in the shoes of others.” This trust-building impact of citizen engagement initiatives was noted as especially valuable, fostering empathy and encouraging solutions oriented towards the common good among individuals who might otherwise not interact. Despite referencing to participants of a particular engagement process, this quote from the interviews is also well illustrative of how lack of trust matters related to climate change adaptation, and the low impact of citizen assemblies at least on the climate system: “What they need now is to be able to push stakeholders to a position in which coming back to the status quo is not acceptable for any of them. In the same way they are pushed by climate change and eventually they will all lose, so they need to come to a systemic alternative; the ecosystem needs to change to bring that different future which is really transformative.”

Another outcome observed was institutional learning. For instance, in one assembly that lacked initial sorting protocols, participants eventually changed the legal framework that streamlined future assemblies. Yet, experts recognized ongoing challenges in achieving real impact, with one stating: “At this point, we have had enough cases of mini publics to know where the difficulties are: legal, fiscal and budgetary dispositions.”

Lastly, citizen engagement was seen as a platform for network-building. In Climathons, for example, participants were able to develop ideas to combat and adapt to climate change while connecting with like-minded individuals. For another initiative that conducted multiple deliberative processes, the aim was to create a regional knowledge pool, helping participants “see the results of a different and transformative way of thinking” and recognize the capacities within the broader value chain.

Overall, experts emphasized that political will and value alignment are critical to achieving real policy impact. Political will, they noted, involves more than just openness to citizen engagement; it includes a commitment to act on the results.

Framing

To illustrate framing with a quote from the interviews, “Everything is biased, but as long as you are clear on how you build the story, it diminishes the impact [of the biases]”. Framing has two components: the stories we tell in all aspects around citizen engagement initiatives, and the culture.

With regards to the framing, and as mentioned in ‘the particularities of climate change (adaptation)’, how the topics are addressed is of key importance. The interviews revealed that it seemed important to bring ‘climate’ closer to the experiences of everyday people. Citizens could establish rapport with their peers by listening how they were impacted by it, as well as by measures put in place. Citizen engagement initiatives could thus consider adopting elements of place-based research into their design. This has implications for how experts are selected, because it opens a wider range of profiles that can be considered as such.

With regards to culture, and interrelated with the framing and the communication strategies, it implies playing attention to the lifestyles and ideas of the location in which the citizen engagement initiative(s) will take place. The ideas are about the overarching conception of participatory processes, the history of the place, and the socio-cultural dynamics between the population.

As an illustrative example, a respondent mentioned how culture may impact outcomes:

“In the [region], with mistrust in the [national] government, they said: ‘why they are lecturing us on how to manage our lands?’. People used to migrate from one land to the other. You can see the cycles very well. You are asking to release just 5% of their land, which is unusable right now, but they are unwilling to do this unless the government pays for it. But the government in [country] is very different on how to interfere on this. They create public funding. But as soon as they saw some doubts, they pulled off. Or a change in government and the new government does not see the point of this. This problem is not there in [country] as the multiple layers of government need to collaborate without disregarding local governments, but they are the ones that are going to uptake the solution.”

Governance

The governance of citizen engagement initiatives also emerged as a theme. The governance implies creating a system by which the different components of citizen engagement—from the actors, the practice and the culture—can be sustained to allow for settling in, in that given policy system. A respondent viewed it “like a common ecosystem, with the actors. The cabinet, the communication director, the project lead, the engagement department, local association, bigger organisation, etc. Ideally you would have citizen representatives. But in any case, transverse”. It would rely on good leadership, with sincerity and “intention”, according to another expert. Implementing such a system would allow for putting in place mechanisms that can more effectively put the knowledge generated into action, as one of the current weaknesses of CEI according to several of the experts. The envisaged structure for the governance could be innovative, flexible, “whilst upholding this mindset of bottom-up system approach”.

As part of the governance there is also the aspect of the budget, as an important aspect due to the realisation of the sheer number of important components needed for conducting (meaningful) citizen engagement. The costliest practices are those that involve random selection, that could reach an estimate of ca. 150€ per person, without counting monetary incentives, depending on the size. However, if making it a standard practice of the government, it can imply millions each year. Some respondents mentioned having organised process for 10.000€.

4.3.3 Part II: Supporting AGORA's Core Goals

This section draws together practices that were mentioned in the interviews that specifically support the four core goals of the AGORA project (Englund et al., 2023). As observed in previous sections, there is some overlap between these themes:

Producing relevant knowledge and action adapted to local needs

It is widely accepted that CEIs can tap in to “collective intelligence” of local citizens and other stakeholders and that this, broadly speaking, opens the door to making decisions that are better calibrated to the local setting. However, achieving this is far from trivial. It requires that CEI organisers invest ongoing efforts to understand the real issues that a place faces, local experience with participation/engagement, the capacities of local actors to support the CEI process, their motivations for initiating a CEI and their plans for what to do with the outcomes. This understanding then calibrates what is relevant for the local area. For example, a CEI in a place with a strong history of civic participation, supported by an established network of outreach and communication actors, seeking a CEI as part of an ongoing and declared package of work by the local government will likely generate different types of knowledge and action to a fledgling CEI that has resulted from popular protest (i.e. a rupture of the status quo).

Perhaps the most important decision is then how to use this understanding to frame the focus of the CEI. What should it generate? Because of what? In order to do what? Formulating a clear output (ideally one based around only a small number of priorities) directs much of the themes below, but also makes it easier to generate something that is genuinely meaningful for local area and easier to follow afterwards. Naming the CEI can connect it to place, giving meaning to local people and creating a mechanism to bind them in a shared ownership (if the CEI's intentions are genuine). Equally, people “don't want to talk about other districts”.

Asking for input before the process has begun can also be a good way to link to the maxi public and generate momentum in local communications and media. This can bring in a large number of ideas, giving organisers some initial scope to work with, gain legitimacy, and build an ongoing interest in the community, and establish a legacy (if these aspects are desired). However, the framing of the concrete focus is important. For example: whether the aim is to identify the most pressing problems that the city should work on, the most promising solutions to implement, how to manage a transition (i.e. the process of adaptation), or all of the above, would generate substantially different types of input.

Once the high-level priorities are set, there is a need to bring this to a local issue of conflict. This may be rooted in a desire to illuminate dilemmas presented by the different values and constraints that members of society hold (where the aim may be to search for some type of consensus or common ground), or be based around a more clear-cut point of contention that is present in the community. However, this needs to be locally tailored while also attuned to national political debate which any CEI is intrinsically embedded in (as national politics is key to shaping views).

During the process, there will generally be a need to filter and prioritise among many options that citizens have suggested (both before and during the CEI). Deliberatively speaking this is often the weakest part of CEI process, and has large potential for distortion by powerful actors (so much so that some interviewees prevent the initiators from doing these types of moderation steps to ensure it is seen to be objective). External experts can weigh in here (e.g. if a proposed solution is unworkable in the local setting because of a regulatory framework, or to provide more details, like direct costs or opportunity costs) or can be trusted to decide but it is key that these stages are transparent, and if the decisions are made by representatives rather than the group as a whole, then this stage is carried by locally respected stakeholders and are in line with the original focus.

Despite presenting a relatively rigid framework until now, it can also be important to ensure there is sufficient flexibility to ensure that citizens feel ownership over the direction of travel (and, e.g., if after discussion there is widespread dislike of the original framing, citizens should be able to adjust it). A nice idea is to ask for participants to propose a work agenda at the end of the first session (this can also link to mutual learning if, e.g., some feel they need more input to understand an issue) and then take ownership of individual themes (for example to name subtasks and teams).

This can also carry over into the outputs or outcomes. For example, if the desired outcome is more locally led action in a certain theme, the agreed next steps may be for societal elites to step back from the organisational aspects (“science is often blocking activism”), or it might be to step into it supporting or institutionalising citizen actions.

Several examples also showed that well-executed CEIs can then generate interest from other parts of local society, generating innovation and entrepreneurship in other levels of government and public institutions as well as the private sector. However, if the next steps are outside of the gift of the organisers/promoters (i.e. it is not about taking a public-sector decision), there is even more need for ongoing support from powerful actors (could be local decision makers or businesses or foundations or social groups, but achieving change needs someone with resources to invest in next steps). These can often require stepping back to be able see the CEI outputs in the round, and include things only tangentially related to the CEI, e.g. providing start-up coaching, seed funding or in-kind support for (social) entrepreneurs.

Achieving just representation and participation

If this is a key goal, then CEIs should proceed with random selection. It’s important that this is understood as being in line with the CEI’s motivation and the local context. For example, if the underlying aim of the CEI is to establish the views of traditionally underrepresented groups, or of a group in particular (e.g. the young, the elderly), a blanket random selection across the population would not be appropriate. The first step is therefore to define the target group in line with the aims of the CEI, and then to proceed with random selection in/prioritising this group.

This may require administrative data that may not be available outside of local government (especially if targeting a population subgroup), meaning this step may require support from beyond the CEI organisers. However, experience suggests CEIs can find unlikely allies for random selection.

For example, many politicians are acutely aware of the power of the established networks within institutions and across society more broadly that can “manipulate the networks”, yet are themselves dependent on local votes, and thus want to hear from the silent majority even if they are not traditionally their supporters. It is also important to consider whether the administrative data is truly representative of the target group (e.g., short-term residents can also contribute to CEI activities especially if they require some ongoing maintenance, and this can be a positive way to enhance local community cohesion in areas with transient populations).

Perhaps the biggest effort required is to persuade people from the target group to join the CEI. This is most challenging for politically marginalised groups, and those that see the idea of CEIs as a political project that is not aligned with their own worldview.

For the first group, efforts have to be made to overcome the barriers that have typically prevented them engaging in local politics and civic life more broadly. Also relevant here, it isn’t just the usual suspects that participate in CEIs, it can also be them who start them. For adaptation issues this is particularly problematic given the crossover between groups that politically marginalised with groups that are most affected by climate impacts. Nonetheless, there is fortunately a large literature on the theory around how to include such groups, even if in practice it remains challenging. In brief, the incentives and logistics to facilitate them joining should be tailored to individual groups or at least to the hardest to reach and can range from choice of location (e.g. is something grand in a town hall at the weekend likely to be attractive to your target group if gravitas or neutrality is important, or would something more intimate one evening in a local day centre be better to show willing to go to the target community) to enabling provisions (e.g. stipends, childcare, translators). For CEIs that are citizen-led, mechanisms by which individuals can suggest and direct the process (e.g. via open WhatsApp groups or online message boards) are helpful (i.e. no need to go through a formal process of acceptance by organisers).

Many of our interviewees also focussed on the fact that CEIs are generally progressive and have a natural tendency towards left-leaning politics. Indeed, some of the CEI projects were initiated by polarizing political contexts and others were, or in the media were portrayed as, projects of left-wing politicians. There were several examples of a clear lack of engagement by centrist and right-leaning political groups in supporting CEIs and awareness of a self-selection bias that keeps conservative-minded citizens, groups, and ideas away from CEIs. In general, we heard that you tend to get participation from those who hold mainstream or “acceptable” views. This presents clear issues for the quality of representative deliberation during the CEI, but also aggravates challenges in implementing any outcomes. As one interviewee said, a key question remains “how can we open up these spaces for people who do not like the climate activists?”

Other interviewees explained it was extremely complicated to bring in diversity in terms of political interest and attitudes with respect to the topic. This is easier—or at least more straightforward—in situations where you have two obvious and widely articulated opposing sides (i.e. where people have social confidence in their views), but for complex challenges like climate adaptation it is often

much harder to identify precise or binary points of conflict. Questionnaires may help to orient the process, but without an established connection it was viewed as unlikely that someone who felt alienated at the start would even answer such a questionnaire to explain their points of disagreement. To complicate things further, while establishing a CEI around a point of conflict is considered good practice, having too many strong views can be detrimental to the quality of the debate, especially if these are only tangentially related to the focus. Thus, it is generally a question of finding balance that depends on the broader political situation and the scale of the conflict that is trying to be resolved.

Despite these challenges, interviewees were positive that with effort you really can get “normal” people who are not the usual suspects to engage in CEIs.

A key way to do this is early messaging to sensitize target groups to the process, for example by raising awareness of the random selection process, to avoid any invitation being seen as spam and discarded. Establishing these communication channels can also maintain a link throughout and after the CEI, potentially supporting legitimacy of the process and the outcomes. The methods of communication need to be tailored to the target group. For example, if you want the views of local young people, advertise via social media and approach youth groups, if you want people to bring their friends, encourage word of mouth and show-and-tell events, if you want to reach people you might not have access to then public broadcasts may help. As one interviewee put it: “You wouldn’t address a single mum in a rural setting the same way you would address a manager in Paris”.

Making use of existing networks and intermediaries and trusted institutions to support the CEI is a widely used tactic. For example, certain groups may be well placed to sponsor or endorse the CEI from afar, while others may be better placed to demonstrate their support by actively participating. Again, how this unfolds depends on the context, issue at hand and target group(s). One option is to engage de-politicised actor groups (e.g. one interviewee suggested it was the endorsement of the fire brigade that catalysed representation; other examples include the sports union or schools) alongside potentially political CSOs that already engage with the target groups, and perhaps lobby on their behalf. Although the aim here is for individual citizens to be involved, some interviewees stressed that this is not always possible as some citizens will always be unwilling or unable to join CEIs, and in which case a second-best option is for trusted intermediaries to bridge the gap as representatives (perhaps shuttling between the CEI and citizens throughout the process – one interviewee suggested that a social worker was particularly able to do this as (s)he had regular contact with the target group and was comfortable in the language used by local administrations). Another point was that citizens can contribute in different ways and to different aspects of a CEI process, i.e., not everyone has to be at every event. This is especially true for hybrid processes where it is possible to operate sub-processes that run at different speeds, with different activities for different groups. In general though, something regular that invites all to contribute and unites the disparate actions or focuses on the core work helps.

However, persuading stakeholder groups to support or join a CEI (especially one that may be seen to be political) may be as hard as persuading citizens, i.e., it will likely take substantial effort and will have to rely on existing networks. It is also important to control for any bias, for example support from a local NGO with strong solidarity roots may help bring some citizens, but may further disincentivize those with more commercial leanings.

Persuading citizens beyond the usual suspects to take part requires ensuring they have the feeling that they will learn something, have fun (or at least not be bored), can contribute to the process (i.e. they have relevant knowledge), and that it is for them (that their knowledge, experience and efforts will be valued). It is important that the CEI is welcoming (and, depending on the context, this may mean familiar) for everyone, or at least the difficult to reach groups. This could involve having an open atmosphere serving coffee and cake on a weekend afternoon or allowing individual groups to self-organise aspects according to their interests.

Once a CEI has established its specific purpose, one of the most impactful ways of engaging citizens in the process is to invest time and effort in effective storytelling. Seeking to understand what triggers emotions, actions and interest in the target group (“what drives them, what do they care about, what concerns them”) then informs the key aspect of how organisers frame the question or problem to solve. This should explain, among other aspects, the reasons for initiating the CEI, who the organisers want to involve, how the issue will affect communities and citizens’ daily lives, which actors are already doing something on this (and, if appropriate, whether it will benefit the target group). Recognising bias here is also important – “yes, it's a little bit biased, but, I'm sorry, for me, everything is a little bit biased” – but if the bias is transparent, it is still possible to involve people if the message is honest. This effective storytelling is a skillset in itself (akin to a form of marketing), that requires preparation and prior research and expertise to understand what has worked before and to adapt any messaging to the local context. This can mean organisers being “humble” and recognising that even if something worked well before any of multiple contextual reasons may limit applicability in the next CEI. Where this is doubt, research and maybe testing to find the right messaging may be useful.

What is “just” depends on what is expected from the citizens and from the organisers, so it is also important to define the degree of participation or engagement of the citizens and of the impacts on next steps. It should be clear from the start whether—irrespective of the deliberative quality of the process—if the main outcomes are raising awareness, activating citizens to change behaviours, or to shape decision making. All are valid aspects of climate change adaptation efforts, but intentionally or unintentionally suggesting that citizen engagement will lead to increased direct democracy that then does not materialise (even if for valid reasons) is extremely detrimental. Despite wide understanding of the challenges associated with this type of tokenism, our interviewees suggested plenty of examples of powerful actors that continue to use CEIs to rubber stamp their decisions (at worst) or not knowing what to do with the CEI outputs (at best).

In a similar vein, biases introduced by any supporting institution or powerful actor need to be transparently acknowledged (especially for financial or in-kind support). These can affect the goals of a CEI (e.g. a condition of support may be to produce investible solutions rather than policy recommendations). This can be even more challenging in smaller areas where there are fewer potential supporting entities and may be further complicated as larger municipalities are also more likely to have in-house resources that can be repurposed to support CEIs. Biases can also impact the CEI process, e.g., whether an evaluation (and what type of evaluation) is required, or even whether there is a proscribed process to follow.

For CEIs that have or may have marked power imbalances, expert facilitation is absolutely key. Without this, and despite any amount of goodwill, better educated and more rhetorically equipped citizens will dominate the discussions, and, without regulation, these different talking contributions will be reflected in the final outputs (but this is often impossible to see in the final output). It is often overlooked how resource intensive this is (and often a surprise to organisers, and thus often a place they try to cut corners) but as well as the process design it is fundamental good practice. To some extent this also depends on the medium chosen for interaction. For example, platform developers we interviewed said it is still unclear if low digital literacy is a barrier to deliberation because they prefer to see things carried out in tandem with offline processes and strong efforts to ensure awareness, communication and support.

Facilitators also play the key role of ensuring that deliberative sessions are kept aligned to the original brief (allowing for flexibility, as described above). This can include limiting the time, space, voice of interest groups present on the day, and ruling discussions and ideas as out of scope. However, this needs to be balanced against the fact that the language and themes covered can really help generate engagement. We heard from several interviewees that directly asking about climate is only going to activate those who are already engaged (and likely only generate the usual suggestions), but if you ask people about their lives and the other things they do and care about there is often a link to climate somewhere and these processes can work better. A concrete example was how discussions that began with what to do with public space often saw climate aspects come through (rather than asking how to make public space more climate resilient from the start).

Before and during the process, it is good practice for facilitators and organisers to recognise that different groups are differently open to new perspectives (children are typically less cynical and less politically influenced, for example) and that different groups absorb the necessary information required to support their deliberation in different ways. For example, online or asynchronous contributions can support those who (want to) take longer to digest information and take part in the debate, as well as providing a way to maintain momentum for the process overall, while others may be best able to contribute on the day with the support of a dedicated expert to explain key themes. In cases where there is hybrid access to information, organisers should ensure that citizens trust that everyone has equal access to the relevant information (e.g. making online and hard copies available). This can extend to other aspects of the process (e.g. allowing citizens within the CEI and

the maxi public to scrutinize parts of the process; like how citizens were invited or how decisions were made). Moreover, bringing in external independent observers to follow the process, or act on a governance board alongside actors involved in the process, can also help ensure justice principles.

Generating mutual learning

Learning doesn't have to be about gaining scientific knowledge. CEIs include different types of learning (about content, about the process, about those involved) and when done well, i.e. when outcomes are widely shared, they can spill over into societal learnings too. As one expert noted when discussing CEIs “no cultural project should be exclusively top-down if you want to matter for society”. However, to matter for a society, it has to be relevant to that society and as such calibrated to the local context. Thus, in terms of societal or institutional learning, present experience with CEIs dictates what can be learned from new ones. For places where CEIs are relatively new, the focus should be on showcasing the process of citizen interaction (worry less about the other aspects as these can be developed with more resources and institutional support); the key aim at early stages is to show that deliberation can generate useful results.

At its centre, deliberation is about understanding why things are important to people as much as what the scientific facts are. Thus, although learning is often understood as a flow of information from experts to lay people, in CEIs it is just as (and perhaps even more) important that knowledge flows between citizens, and from citizens to experts and organisers (and to other experts and organisers via peer knowledge sharing platforms). As one expert put it, we should see CEIs as opportunities for recognising that “climate change is not an abstract concept: it’s part of the everyday” and to flip the dynamic: “We always try to engage citizens [in our science projects], and it should be the other way around:...engaging science in citizens’ lives”. An effective way to achieve this is to ask questions like “why can’t we do X”. One of our interviewees suggested that most people are interested in “saving the environment”, but struggle with prioritising which goals to pursue and which parts of society have to exit their own “mini comfort zones”. Another commented that we don’t give enough space for people to air their fears about climate change and the interconnection between climate, weather, emotion, local history and daily life.

Presenting a clear puzzle to solve together is a good way to overcome this as having a genuinely shared problem helps shrink “differences, gaps or disparities between groups”. However, this does not happen instantly. Instead, all actors involved need to try to (and to be willing to) occupy other people’s shoes. Often this requires dedicating a part of the process to getting to know others as people and building group empathy, especially before introducing views on polarising topics. It’s important to create some relatability that helps with the acceptance of ideas and perspectives as coming from a place of good faith (“I know this person is a good person, so I will listen to their point and try to understand where they are coming from”). Techniques that focus on listening and reflecting on others views are often important, especially if they include attempts to find some commonalities. Open questions (“what would you imagine if...”) can be a good way to create shared empathy and get to know each other and to foment “unlikely combinations of people and

conversations”. The mutual learning here is “I understand your point of view” not necessarily “We agree” on the best outcome. A point we heard that one of the key outputs of CEIs is not that people change their minds, but that the process helps them realise there are lots of solutions (not just one or two). This can help with those suffering climate anxiety, but also is a key way to bring along people with different views about climate change, and what to do about it.

There is, nonetheless, usually a need to impart some information to CEI participants that contextualises the task at hand. Where possible, when providing new information, good practices include asking if there is another way it could be provided and being flexible in offering substitute delivery formats that also recognise that different people grasp new information at different speeds (e.g. written material including online and printed, presentations / webinars, discussions, town halls etc.). Learnings might not be what are expected (for example one interviewee suggested that an outcome of the CEI was to reduce the trust in the way that international climate policymaking was reported in the national media). Design processes based on what is happening at that moment and the different capacities or preferences of different groups and during discussions don’t let experts talk incessantly. Organisers and facilitators should ensure experts are available to support the process, not to dominate it, though achieving this requires facilitation experience and experts that are open to being silenced. Equally, information doesn’t have to come directly from experts: sometimes asking locals (e.g. schoolchildren) to (re-)interpret aspects of the challenges or solutions for the rest of the group can show a totally different perspective and presentation style to what people are used to hearing. The idea of “giving climate change a face” illustrates the importance of art and narrative formation.

Producing improved collaboration

Organisers and facilitators should create an environment within the CEI process that fosters collaboration, for example as mentioned above, the need to build group empathy before introducing potentially polarising discussions. Picking the right size of group is also important. Although having too few participants creates issues for legitimacy and representativeness, if the group is too big it becomes “too heavy” – requiring ever more expert facilitation and multiplying the effort required by all involved to align around shared outputs. Collaboration is also affected by other process choices, like the method or tools used (e.g. online tools are great for generating ideas and simple up or down voting, for asynchronous discussion, and being open to an almost unlimited number of citizens, but are much less helpful for emotive issues where facilitated discussion or serious games involving scenarios and role-playing can help find better (if not best) solutions). Equally, the output of collaboration in CEIs should be seen as the search for some common(ish) ground rather than an often-unattainable consensus. As with other themes covered above, investing in evaluation during the process and a flexibility to accommodate the findings is important to ensure collaborative goals are being met.

It is necessary to protect the group empathy and the deliberative space from outside influences and (pre-)existing power dynamics. This includes considering who provides input, when and how.

Beyond informational sessions, those with specific expertise can support the process via checking the feasibility of any ideas generated, “securing the facts” and providing feedback to citizens in an objective way. Experts can also collaborate to help the facilitators see links between ideas and themes, connecting ideas and avoiding content missteps, and suggest others that may be able to speak to certain issues. These experts do not have to be independent or even objective themselves—especially in conflict issues it is likely that will not be. Instead, they can be specifically selected to provide a point of view or explain their experience. The important aspect to ensure a collaborative environment is to ensure that any bias (including political if relevant) is transparent.

Other links to the outside world—especially to the maxi public—are highly context specific, depending on (among other things) the relationship between citizens and local (partisan) politics, and individuals’ views on whether the citizens in the mini-public represent them and whether they are sufficiently competent to make decisions for all. CEIs are often an empowering, and in some cases “life-changing”, process for those that take part with citizens often reporting a feeling that they can make a difference to politics, policies and decision making. However, while some interviewees suggested that if a clear majority of 80–90% of a mini public declare a position, this is a good benchmark for broader acceptance, another pointed to emerging research that shows that CEIs have limited potential to impact the views of the maxi public. For example, while effective communication can convince those who are ambivalent to the strength of (direct) democracy, the core theme discussed or on the proposed outcomes, these tend to be in a minority on issues like climate change adaptation and the majority of the maxi public (who hold extreme views on these themes) are unlikely to change their minds because of a CEI.

Collaboration also requires that the CEI is seen to be purposeful. This requires clear sight of next steps after the CEI and a realistic view of the pace of achieving any change in the given context. In part this requires coming to terms with how the CEI and topic in focus interacts with local politics. For example, it may be necessary for local actors to take an unpopular decision that is not aligned with the CEI outputs (or not at the pace required). This is clearly not ideal, but should be expected in the real world and has to be transparently explained if CEIs are to (re)build trust in democratic systems (or not!). Indeed, without meaning to dent a belief in the power of CEIs, one of our interviewees noted “they are not a magic bullet”. Instead, CEIs are—and should be seen as—part of a portfolio of options available to our polities to advance climate adaptation action. Equally, CEI providers should be clear eyed about the potential for change (we spoke to one who has stopped working with staid national institutions because “you spend more time complying to tender requirements” than helping citizens create innovative climate solutions).

To some degree, the CEI outputs can also shape ongoing collaboration during the process. For example, if the aim is to produce guidelines or work priorities these can have natural follow-ons whereas long lists of recommended solutions are infamous for getting lost in bureaucratic systems. An option that has largely not been explored is whether CEIs can function as a checks-and-balances

tool with citizens acting as juries that approve or reject the suggestions of another form of decision making (e.g. technocracy).

Even with transparency, the period between the CEI concluding and any impact is important for the strength of the broader CEI environment. For example, if it takes six months for an institution to respond to a CEI outcome this dents trust in the process, even if this is clear in advance. Monitoring and communicating follow-on steps is good practice, but relatively rare given it is a big resource requirement that likely requires institutional support when everyone in the administration has “gone back to their day job” and citizens have gone back to their daily lives. Naming a public servant as responsible for periodic reporting (even if only updating a website every quarter with any progress) or forming a CEI advocate group can help maintain the pressure needed to keep the CEI visible. If resource challenges are hard for institutions, they are even harder for citizen-led actions: to continue the momentum a CEI generates: “you need someone who's really engaged and who has a network and who has a plan and everything. Otherwise those things die.”

4.4 Peer-learning workshop 3

This section describes the results of the third peer-learning workshop (PLW3), which took place online on the 13th December 2024, with 20 attendees (6 external experts, and 14 members of the AGORA consortium). As mentioned in Section 3.2, PLW3 covered three main topics, which are discussed in turn below. Owing to the short time between the workshop and the submission of this deliverable, these are preliminary results only; a full synthesis of the findings will be prepared in early 2025.

4.4.1 Contextual factors and enabling environment (Topic A)

Table 8 shows the wide range of contextual factors (that can be both enablers and constraints) for designing purposeful citizen engagement practices gathered during the work carried out for this deliverable. These were presented to participants during the first part of the workshop.

Table 8: Contextual factors intervening in citizen engagement initiatives

Category	Themes
Socio-cultural	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local cultural norms and values: The cultural attitudes toward participation, deliberation, and collaboration impact how citizens engage. For example, in some regions, deliberation and public discussion are well-accepted, while in others, they are seen as unnecessary or confrontational. • Social movements and historical experience: Movements like Spain’s Indignados (2011) influenced the public perception of engagement. Contexts with a history of social movements tend to have higher public interest in participation. • Familiarity with deliberative democracy: Some regions (like Scandinavia and Benelux) have more established traditions of consensus-building, while in other areas (like Central and Eastern Europe), citizen engagement may seem “bizarre” or unfamiliar.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Trust in public institutions: Contexts with low trust in government or public bodies tend to require additional transparency and accountability mechanisms to engage citizens meaningfully.
Political and governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political climate and government buy-in: Political support for engagement varies widely. Authoritarian-leaning governments may see engagement as a threat, while democratic governments may embrace it for legitimacy. • Election cycles and political change: The lifespan of a citizen engagement initiative can be disrupted if there's a change in political leadership or priorities. • Institutional openness to engagement/co-production: Public authorities may resist power-sharing or remain reluctant to shift decision-making power to citizens, especially if this challenges existing hierarchies. • Legal and regulatory frameworks: In some cases, legal mandates exist that require citizen engagement (e.g., EU directives on public participation). However, without such mandates, engagement becomes voluntary and more fragile. • Regional differences: There are stark regional differences in the adoption of citizen engagement. Central and Eastern Europe have lower adoption rates, while Scandinavia and Benelux have long traditions of public deliberation.
Economic and financial	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of funding and resources: Engagement requires money for logistics, facilitation, communication, and compensation for participants. Lack of funding can limit engagement scope, especially in marginalized communities. • Marketization of democracy: Experts noted that there is a growing "competitive market" for citizen engagement, with funding sources like the EU promoting competition among organizations to "sell democracy." • Compensation and incentives: Citizens are more likely to participate when there are clear incentives (e.g., financial compensation, meals, child care, or skills development opportunities). • Economic inequality: Economic inequality shapes engagement, as wealthier citizens may have more flexibility (time, money, knowledge) to participate, while marginalized groups may face barriers like unpaid care work or job constraints.
Social and demographic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Population demographics: Age, gender, and education levels influence how people engage. For example, older citizens may prefer in-person engagement, while younger generations may be comfortable online. • Social diversity and inclusion: Engaging underrepresented groups requires additional efforts to overcome language, literacy, and accessibility barriers. Gender balance and representation of marginalized groups are often explicit goals in CEIs. • Existing social capital: If communities have strong networks and social ties (e.g., local community groups or neighborhood associations), it becomes easier to engage them.
Geographic and environmental	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Urban vs. rural settings: Urban areas often have more engagement due to higher population density, but rural areas may require place-based approaches and attention to rural-urban divides.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate change relevance: In the context of climate adaptation, citizens in regions more affected by climate hazards (like floods, wildfires, or heatwaves) may feel more urgency to engage. • Physical location of events: If engagement is in-person, citizens may be excluded if locations are not easily accessible (remote areas, inadequate public transport, etc.).
Technological and digital	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to technology and digital literacy: The shift to digital engagement (due to COVID-19) revealed that not everyone has equal access to reliable internet or knowledge of online tools. • Digital platforms for engagement: Citizen engagement platforms have become common, but familiarity with these platforms varies, particularly for elderly or marginalized groups. • (Added) Cybersecurity and data privacy: Digital participation requires guarantees that citizens' data is protected, which can influence whether people feel safe engaging online.

The results shown in **Figure 10** show participants responses to being asked to carry out three actions for each factor if:

- they had seen that contextual factor impacting a citizen engagement initiative (+);
- if it was controllable or just manageable (a circle, black and white respectively);
- and whether there were relationships between factors, which would impact or reinforce each other (→). **Figure 10**

Figure 10: Miro board output for Topic A on contextual factors

The post-its indicated which solutions could diminish the impact of constraining contextual factors. Participants listed the following:

- Framing and language used based on the group to be engaged
- Flexibility to adapt frameworks
- Include funding in the legal framework
- Work with existing civil society organisations or umbrella networks (organisers)
- Collaborate with intermediary actors
- Provide incentives and support for participation for those that have less means to participate
- Improving networks using digital tools
- Organising also in person event, not just providing a platform to vote or express opinions
- Ideally, digital tools should be used to complement and enhance in-person participatory processes and not stand alone
- Digital platforms should be transparent by design. Code, participants' contributions and processes' outcomes should be visible and accessible to the wider public.

These results show similarities with best practices that emerged during the interviews, for example, related to framing, flexibility, as well as the creation of alliances with civil society organisations.

4.4.2 Knowledge transmission (Topic B)

The second topic reflected the complexity of sharing knowledge about citizen engagement given the wealth of knowledge that is already available in platforms, and which has accumulated via the work of practitioners and the academic community. The prompts were which knowledge type participants had either created (through AGORA or other projects) or knew about, and which actor would benefit the most from receiving it.

The Miro board (**Figure 11**) illustrates the pathways and mechanisms for knowledge transmission between these key actors in citizen engagement initiatives. Central to this process are various communication tools and platforms—such as dashboards, webinars, blogs, and policy briefs—that facilitate the flow of information across these different stakeholder groups. Experts were seen on having a pivotal role in coordinating and disseminating knowledge through activities like conferences, workshops, and the sharing of good practices, mostly towards initiators, organisers and facilitators. However, as these actors connect with participants and advisors, using outputs such as guidelines, guidebooks, and newsletters, could also foster from their side collaborative learning particularly in climate adaptation processes.

Additionally, targeted communication strategies, like tailored communication and media products, aim to engage the maxi-public and opposition while addressing gaps such as how to reach broader audiences with specialized knowledge. The inclusion of evidence-based materials—policy briefs, journal articles, and knowledge repositories—would strengthen the credibility of shared insights and supports decision-making processes. Importantly, the interconnected flow highlights the need for tailored engagement strategies to ensure effective knowledge transfer and uptake, aligning with the diverse needs and roles of the actors involved.

Figure 11: Miro board outputs for Topic B on knowledge transmission

4.4.3 Designing a citizen engagement initiative (Topic C)

The last part of the workshop aimed at putting everything together that emerged during the data gathering activities, and that linked the elements of purposeful design together. **Figure 12** shows the illustration of the ‘complex web of factors’ that citizen engagement initiatives consist of:

SCENARIOS

CONTRAINTS

- Election period:** This process coincides with an election year, increasing uncertainty.
- Policy deadline pressure:** Engagement process must be completed before a policy deadline.
- Social conflict:** Disagreements arise between different community groups.
- Extreme weather event:** An unexpected flooding destroys part of the city.

Possible option 2 constraints:

- Community resistance:** Local community refuse to participate due to distrust.
- Cybersecurity breach:** Sensitive participant data is leaked online.
- Polarization of the process:** Media frames the engagement as politically biased.
- Sudden political turnover:** New government leadership changes priorities on citizen engagement (low priority).
- Budget cuts:** The participant that received this card has to return money.

Board game
Fixed (e.g. # cards set the game)

Online game
You can choose the constraints

OPTIONALITY

- A given number of cards (#) set the scenario
- More constraints are given to participants across the project

Resources

At the beginning of the game, the participant(s) receive a series of resources. In everytime step, participants get X number of coins.

Rule: with the budget you can 'buy' design features, with the other resources the value of the design features decreased.
Rule: you can 'buy' resources (staff, knowledge, time)

fixed budget

staff

knowledge

time

QUESTION 1: 'constraint' cards for 'setting the scenario' and 'during the game constraints' should be the same, or they are two different lists?

QUESTION 2: This will imply that design features have a 'value'. How to decide on how much they cost is possible? Will the cost change depending on constraints or passive players support/opposition?

Design features

These are the design features you can collect ("buy") across the game. They could come with "points" linked to an expected "Impact/positive externality".

SOME EXAMPLES	# of days	permanent deliberative space	citizen engagement consultancy services	communication services
random selection	facilitators	digital tool for engagement	capacity-building workshop	
accessibility measures	stakeholder mapping	conflict mediation services	monitoring & evaluation system	
public consultation portal	participant incentives	live translators/ interpreters	...	

QUESTION 3: If each of these cards comes with 'points' linked to a certain impact/positive externality, this could give winning/losing hierarchies to players. How to link 'features' with impacts & externalities though?

Players

Active players

- Local authority
- Citizens
- Social movements
- Initiators

Passive players

- Advisors
- Experts
- Sponsors
- Media
- Maxi-public
- Opposition

Active players: game participants receive a player. Can come already with X number of resources, changing depending on player.

Passive players: They may have supporting or opposition roles. For instance, the 'opposition - advisor' could be starting a legal procedure against the initiative. Then you have to spend more budget on certain other resources.

Points: design features come with points towards 'achievements'

Goal of the game

DESIGN A CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT INITIATIVE

When the game ends, people will have a set of design features which would have dealt with the constraints of the context, the available resources and the support or opposition of passive players. The design features will have points, which participants can sum to see the "best citizen engagement designer".

If it was an online game:
This feature choices could recommend a "best fitting type of initiative", with linked resources to bring it forward.

Relevant knowledge and action – aligned with the local context, policy priorities, and social dynamics, and enjoy support and acceptance among actors.

Just participation – voices and participation of citizens and other stakeholders including the marginalized and disadvantaged are bolstered.

Mutual learning – citizens, decision makers, researchers, and other stakeholders learn from one another.

Improved collaboration – partnerships are based on trust and respect among citizens, decision makers, researchers, and other stakeholders.

- Empowerment
- Be in each other's shoes
- Transformative experiences
- Permanent deliberative space
- Mutually desirable futures
- New or stronger networks
- Increased optimism
- Clarity in own positionings
- More inclusive policies
- Improved city liveability

QUESTION 4: We want to highlight the point that different design features will lead to different impacts or achieving other positive 'externalities'. Would the game do a good job visualising this?

Figure 12: Miro board input for Topic C on designing a citizen engagement initiative

The Miro board shows the potential of designing a serious game based on all the information gathered on citizen engagement, aiming to link contextual factors, resource availability, actors and design choices, and the reaching of certain goals. The questions to the participants were the following:

- Fit-for-purpose: Is this a good way to transmit knowledge about citizen engagement? How could we help (not hinder) the flow of knowledge? (where could we play it – in person, online, individually in groups...).
- Generalisable: The 'value decisions': is it possible with the available information to put a value on a design feature? does the value change by context?
- Awareness-raising: How to better represent climate change adaptation particularities?

- Adaptable to multiple perspectives: How could we include the different perspectives (cards from the report)? How could we make it relevant to different "players"?

Participants mentioned that it could be a good way to learn about designing citizen engagement, and contain layers of complexity, by which people could decide how much information they would be receiving about each item.

5. Conclusion and next steps

Climate adaptation action is increasingly taking place in hybrid network and deliberative governance forms at the local level. This trend is the result of a self-reinforcing web of factors including: the need to complement traditional top-down and market-based approaches to climate adaptation; the cross-sectoral impacts of climate change; an increase in public awareness that climate change is already affecting Europe across governance levels, and a growing belief among policymakers that engaging with citizens and other stakeholders can both enhance the outcomes of policy-making processes and reinforce democratic ideals more broadly. As a result—and supported by initiatives by the European Union, national, and subnational governments—the number of citizen engagement initiatives focused on climate adaptation appears to have grown substantially.

The aim of this report has been to gather different sources of evidence related to the practice and design of citizen engagement initiatives for climate change adaptation action. The twin focus (on engaging citizens, rather than on stakeholders more broadly and on engagement in climate-change related decision-making, rather than all societal challenges) helped us to better understand good and bad practices related to engaging this specific stakeholder group in this specific theme. This complements work ongoing more broadly on identifying and engaging other stakeholder groups (e.g. Baulenas et al., 2023; SEI Tool) and multi-sector or general guidelines for citizen engagement (see Sections 3.1 and 4.1), though a clear finding from our work was that context (e.g. societal sector, stakeholder group, climate change hazard, scale) is of key importance in designing effective citizen engagement initiatives for climate change action.

The research questions that guided the data collection activities were whether and how (un)learning has occurred as CEI practices have evolved within specific communities of practice. Specifically, the aim was to observe which practices had developed and which not, and to which factors could explain it. Also, whether there were innovations happening and what role played the particularities of climate change. In this case, the results indeed show how the emergence of climate-related concerns upon urban and rural areas has been one of the steering factors for opting for citizen engagement to strengthen societal responses. However, the concern continues to be whether it has a real impact on policies (Gaventa and Barrett, 2011; Ross et al., 2021), as also emerging in our interviews.

Among the sources of evidence, we reviewed citizen engagement guidelines from several international organisations. Across these guidelines, the practitioner's knowledge is as present as

the academic, and most of them are directed towards public authorities. To face the vast quantity of information there exists on citizen engagement (see Deliverable 1.1), these documents continue to be a good resource geared towards maintaining the principles of citizen engagement, generally actionable and contributing to capacity building and continuity.

Interestingly, the guidelines not only cover mini-publics as one of the standard and often opted-for approaches (Deliverable 1.1: Mapping of citizen engagement initiatives). Several other types of engagement were reported upon, similarly as emerging from the interviews. This is the case for instance for open spaces of deliberation which serve as a place where citizens can share their anxieties and concerns, and construct together possible desirable futures opening the range of solutions they initially could envisage (see e.g. Krauß, 2023). In this sense, the practice of discursive deliberation may deliver on its promises: “producing reasonable, well-informed opinions in which participants are willing to revise preferences in light of discussion, new information, and claims made by fellow participants.” (Chambers, 2003, p. 309). To support openness and informed opinion-formation, it is important that knowledge on best practices for different types of citizen engagement continues to be shared and reaches the right stakeholders and actors involved in the process.

What was generally missing in the guidelines but emerged through the interviews, was a contextualisation of best practices. For instance, the available resources will determine how a given type of citizen engagement (e.g. a climate assembly), achieves its purposes. For example, the availability of resources is strongly related to contextual factors such as political and governance factors, which will contain or enable successful citizen engagement. Socio-economic, demographic and cultural factors will also determine the easiness in which engagement finds a place, and how (Willis et al., 2022). Thus, to provide a best practice decontextualised, may render the practice of less use.

Another element that emerged strongly in the interviews and in the workshops was the process of (un)learning, by which a citizen engagement process may, for example, lose the trust from their participants, opposition may impact how legitimate the results are perceived by the broader public, or some initiatives may only respond to the interests of a few, rather than to the public good. However, the complex fabric of citizen engagement, made of multiple influencing actors, contextual factors, practices and design choices across engagement stages, should never deter an actor to opt for it, as the intangibles may speak louder than its visible outputs (Blue, 2017).

Overall and when well conducted, citizen engagement seems to be illustrated in this sentence: “is there something that you and us (...) could do better together?”. A key part -but also a component of- a stronger democracy but parallel to other forms of creating solutions for climate change adaptation. As we aimed to highlight, it is not the panacea, but it should be seen as a set of processes that if well conducted, can bring many more additional positive outcomes.

Next steps

The next steps of this research are several. On the one hand, to synthesise these lessons and contribute to the adaptation AGORA project’s main outputs and legacy, such as the Climate

Adaptation Citizen engagement digital handbook. Our aim is to produce material that can be actionable for different types of contexts and goals of the citizen engagement initiative. The main target groups are initiators (public authorities, citizens, civil society organisations), who aim to introduce deliberative practices in support of policy-making processes related to climate change adaptation, without failing to also address the other actors and stakeholders relevant for a successful process. On the other hand, this research will be formatted also in the form of a research article, to be able to contribute to the literature on citizen engagement and reach the academic community and practitioners. Finally, by producing these additional outputs together with this deliverable, the next steps involve thus dissemination and outreach activities, as well as a contribution to the exploitation activities planned within AGORA to have an impact on the Mission Adaptation principal goals.

6. Bibliography

- African Union Development Agency - NEPAD. (n.d.). *African Union handbook on citizen engagement*. NEPAD. P. 1-56.
- Baulenas, E., Bojovic, D., Urquiza, D., Terrado, M., Pickard, S., González, N., & Clair, A. S. (2023). User selection and engagement for climate services coproduction. *Weather, Climate, and Society*, 15(2), 381-392.
- Blue, G. (2017). *Participatory and deliberative approaches to climate change*. In *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Climate Science*.
- Carpini, M. X. D., Cook, F. L., & Jacobs, L. R. (2004). *Public deliberation, discursive participation, and citizen engagement: A review of the empirical literature*. *Annual Review of Political Science*, 7, 315-344. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2007.9685637>
- EIT-Climate KIC. (accessed October 2024). *The Climathon playbook*. EIT-Climate KIC. Online resource.
- European Commission. (2024). *Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/736 of 1 March 2024 on a Code of Practice on citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 185, 1–10.
- Evaeus, B. (ED.) (2021). *Transforming cities together: a public engagement guide for cities*. Guide. CIVOCRACY/WWF. 1-61.
- Gaventa, J., & Barrett, G. (2010). *So what difference does it make? Mapping the outcomes of citizen engagement*. *IDS Working Papers*, 2010(347), 01-72.
- Hörschelmann, K., Werner, A., Bogacki, M., & Lazova, Y. (2019). *Taking Action for Urban Nature: Citizen Engagement Handbook*. *NATURVATION Guide*, 1–36.
- Jacobs, L. R., Cook, F. L., & Carpini, M. X. D. (2009). *Talking together: Public deliberation and political participation in America*. University of Chicago Press.
- Jaubin, J. (ED.), et al. (2021). *Citizen Engagement Solution Booklet*. *EU Smart Cities Information System*. European Commission. 1-49.
- Krauß, W. (2023). Slowing down climate services: Climate change as a matter of concern. *Sustainability*, 15(8), 6458.
- MIP4ADAPT. (2023). *Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Adaptation: A DIY Manual*. Manual.

- OECD. (2022). *OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes. OECD Public Governance Reviews*. OECD Publishing, Paris. <https://doi.org/10.1787/f765caf6-en>. P. 1-94.
- Pickard, S., & Baulenas, E. (2024). Citizen Engagement Practices That Promote Justice, Mutual Learning, and Collaboration in Situated Climate Adaptation Initiatives. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 105(12), E2294-E2299.
- Ross, A., Van Alstine, J., Cotton, M., & Middlemiss, L. (2021). *Deliberative democracy and environmental justice: Evaluating the role of citizens' juries in urban climate governance. Local Environment*, 26(12), 1512-1531.
- Stec, S., Abat, A., Hafen, F., Niestroy, I., & Sperrin, Á. (2020). *Frameworks for citizen engagement in the European Green Deal: The REAL DEAL handbook. European Environmental Bureau (EEB)*, 1-84.
- WHO. (2024). *Citizen engagement in evidence-informed policy-making: A guide to mini-publics*. Geneva: World Health Organization. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. P. 1-106.
- Willis, R., Curato, N., & Smith, G. (2022). *Deliberative democracy and the climate crisis. Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change*, 13(2), e759.

Appendix

Appendix 1: Glossary of methods/innovative mechanisms for CE

Method	Explanation	Examples
Based around talking		
Interviews	Typically formal and usually with one or few citizens at a time. Structure and sometimes the questions to be asked are often designed before to give comparable results from parallel interviews.	
Surveys	Participants fill out a series of questions to seek their views on certain predetermined themes. They could do this individually or in small groups.	
Focus groups	Small groups of citizens are gathered to discuss a (usually pre-determined) set of topics. The conversations may be facilitated or may be free flowing. Among many potential goals, the outputs can help to test already formed ideas, generate new ones, or see how citizens debate issues.	
Meetings	Formal encounters that bring individual citizens into dialogue with other citizens and (usually) non-citizens (e.g. decision makers). Can be online or offline.	
Public hearings	Formal meetings where arguments are presented about an issue from different perspectives. Citizens' may be invited to actively participate (e.g. provide evidence) or may be engaged during the decision-making process. Note: this does not include activities where citizens have no opportunity to meaningfully contribute to the deliberative activities (e.g. one-way "public consultations" or "public awareness" events).	Citizen juries
Informal conversation spaces	These events are usually open to everyone and create opportunities for people to discuss their thoughts about themes in an unstructured and informal way. These settings seek to overcome some of the power imbalances in more formalised settings. These may have a defined output (e.g. an informal discussion about a local issue), or may try to gather people interested in discussing broader themes.	Conversation cafes
Online forums	Often part of online platforms, these function in a similar way to offline forums in that they allow citizens to discuss their views on different topics, but through being online they allow interaction at a time that is more convenient for participants.	
Webinars and live streams	Online meetings allowing remote participants to engage (either by asking questions in webinars or by voting following live streams).	
Based around working together		

Workshops	Creative, interactive meetings where teams work together on a set issue. Can include a broad range of aims, from solving a problem, developing knowledge, producing a plan, or identifying a problem for future engagement.	
Civic hackathons	A specific type of workshop where a group of citizens (sometimes working in smaller groups and sometimes with guidance from technical experts) work together to discuss problems, ideate solutions, and present them back to the organisers and wider group at the end. They are often intense 'design sprint' activities that can run in a single day or can run over several days.	Climathons - https://climathon.climate-kic.org/
Participatory arts	These events permit participants to collaboratively communicate their points of view in a wider variety of ways than in most settings (i.e. they go beyond standard reports / voting).	Photovoice , participatory mapping
Field data collection	A type of participatory research (citizen science), citizens either work independently, in groups, or with experts to gather data related to investigating, monitoring or resolving a climate change issue.	Species census, Park Re-Design , Participatory mapping
Based around capacity building		
Training sessions	Capacity building sessions with a pre-identified theme that is linked to a specific climate change adaptation action.	
Experiential and immersive education	Citizens are taken (physically or virtually) to where the causes or impacts are felt to understand the reality of what the problems mean and to give them insights into how they might be solved.	Guided walks; shadowing (e.g. 'day in the life of...')
Miscellaneous (could apply to any of the above)		
Research or experimental method	These are untested processes where, alongside generating (hopefully beneficial) outcomes, part of the focus is to generate knowledge of the process itself.	
Personalised communication	A form of engaging citizens in which information providers make the issue specifically relevant to individuals or individual groups (rather than providing generalised information that individuals must then interpret for themselves).	
Interactive content	This can be online or offline, but involves some sort of content that reacts to participants' inputs. This could predefined (e.g. an app that visualises the impact of citizens' choices on a local landscape) or part of an interactive codesign process	
Participatory research	Participants collaborate with each other and sometimes other stakeholders to expand the knowledge base relevant to a specific issue.	

Mobile apps	Mobile-phone specific form of engagement. Usually individual. Can involve dialogue (i.e. via forums), voting or interactive content. Also, see Gamification and Online Platforms.	Decidim.bcn
Online platforms	Online platforms provide a wide range of opportunities for engagement and knowledge sharing. For example, may include (interactive) content like webinars, online forums, a decision-making system (e.g. online voting) and online meetings (and/or streaming/recordings of in-person meetings)	
Gamification	Commonly conducted via smartphone apps (but can be online or offline as well). Present citizens with an opportunity to contribute or learn in an entertaining way. Can involve scoring points for correct answers or competing against/collaborating with peers to respond to certain challenges. The deliberative aspect is rare, but theoretically possible (e.g. if people get points for submitting their view).	

Appendix 2: PLW1 Full Results - Synthesised good practices for citizen engagement in climate adaptation initiatives

From: Pickard & Baulenas (Accepted) 'Citizen engagement practices that promote justice, mutual learning and collaboration in situated climate adaptation initiatives'. *BAMS*.

Supplementary Information: Table S1 - Collected good practices for citizen engagement in adaptation action.

Stage	Example practices
Producing relevant knowledge and action adapted to local needs	
Context and purpose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify what makes the local context special and unique Avoiding over generalizing / universalizing Test any assumptions made about the local context Planning sufficient time to understand context Actively factor in (in time, budget and expertise) the efforts needed to understand the local context Immersing the process and the organizers in the local context In situ preparation Make the effort to lay the ground or provide context for the project Adapt the planning process to involve citizens Tailor the entire process to the local context Adapt the process to engaging local communities to understand their needs and topics of interest
Pre-engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Understanding the context Set out plans to identify / accommodate different accessibility requirements Plan a combination of different learning strategies/methods accordingly Designing an appropriate range of learning methods/strategies aiming to include everyone Introduce the project/activity in advance Go beyond engaging with the 'usual suspects' (i.e. those that already participate in similar processes) Taking a bottom-up, interactive approach to process design
On-the-day engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Immersive experience (e.g., living with the community) Case-studies (real-life experiences, local data, and field visits) are used to communicate issues at hand Actively listening to citizens to understand local/regional/national needs and gaps Explicitly recognizing the importance of bringing different groups' knowledge/experience together and the value of each as part of the whole Integration and recognition of different knowledge

	<p>Participants are made to feel they belong as part of a common project (even more efforts required for citizens)</p> <p>Consider alternative (formal and informal) methods (e.g. experiential learning).</p>
Post-engagement	<p>Sufficient planning/provision of resources (process time, finances participant capacity)</p> <p>Share and identify evaluation criteria earlier in the project (more important when adapting to citizens)</p> <p>Clearly define specific/tailored evaluation/monitoring methods</p> <p>Tailoring the communications of the results/outcomes to the different target groups</p> <p>Actively adapt dissemination and in-person communication styles (language, delivery style, accessibility).</p> <p>Provide to participants in an easily accessible way, the material used, the information collected, and the next steps agreed on</p> <p>Clearly define next steps</p>
Achieving just representation and participation	
Context and purpose	<p>Prior research to understand vulnerabilities, socioeconomic characteristics of the target population and power dynamics (e.g. through surveys, champions, embedded researchers)</p> <p>Seek to identify issues of power</p> <p>Tailoring existing models of working to the target groups' needs, or developing new ones.</p> <p>Seek to correct issues of power (e.g. preventing dominant voices from directing the process)</p> <p>Conduct explicit stakeholder mapping to identify key actors and ensure that the mapped stakeholders / civil society organizations comprehensively cover the target citizen population (i.e. avoid gaps)</p> <p>Identifying key target groups (especially paying attention to those who are traditionally underrepresented or known to be vulnerable)</p> <p>For the identified vulnerabilities and relevant socioeconomic characteristics: develop purposeful communication strategy;</p> <p>Engagement of representatives of these groups</p>
Pre-engagement	<p>Addressing power imbalances (institutional, knowledge, capacity) through design: smaller groups, provide background knowledge in a pre-engagement event, survey to identify barriers to engagement by target groups, breaking down topic complexity</p> <p>Going beyond existing networks (i.e. not just listening to the same 'voices')</p> <p>Strategic / planned participant selection</p> <p>Stratified, representative and purposeful sampling</p> <p>Purposive selection of which citizens to include to reflect aim / context (e.g. ensuring gender balance, ensuring vulnerable groups present)</p>

	<p>Collaborate with champion brokers or impartial expert advisers (who can be the bridge with vulnerable groups and inform about barriers to engagement) + tailor collaboration with champion brokers or expert advisers to respective target audience</p> <p>Creative, open, tailored, engaging communication which helps in achieving the goals</p> <p>Clear plans to identify / accommodate accessibility requirements</p> <p>Ensuring adequate planning / provision of resources (process time, finances, participant capacity)</p>
<p>On-the-day engagement</p>	<p>Accessibility (logistics, support – e.g. babysitting provided to enable people to participate outside of their day jobs)</p> <p>Sufficient attention paid to individuals to ensure no participant’s engagement is limited by their accessibility needs</p> <p>Effective moderation (facilitator capacity/positionality, time available and resources required all sufficient to address critical situations)</p> <p>Trained facilitators that are tailored to working with (target) citizen groups, who can design a process where everyone feels comfortable to speak and limit the “space” of powerful actors</p> <p>Use facilitation techniques that focus on equity, diversity, inclusion; striving to empower participants to contribute and feel their voice is heard</p> <p>Active facilitation recognizes and corrects for power imbalances in group discussion and decision making</p> <p>Communication practices: non-violent communication, speaking in rounds, bottom-up approach (hearing everyone’s voices)</p> <p>Listening to everyone’s voice and ensuring no one individual’s priorities dominate the process</p> <p>Creative communication methods to engage with target citizen groups (e.g. playdough)</p> <p>Clearly accounting for on-the-day representation in the outputs (e.g. the number/distribution of participants will determine the weight of views in the outputs)</p> <p>Identifying, recognizing and correcting for overt and hidden power dynamics that can impact the process</p> <p>Value individuals’ knowledge explicitly</p> <p>Recognize participants as experts in their field and invite them to share their knowledge</p>
<p>Post-engagement</p>	<p>Making participants feel valued and that the process/outputs are valuable to them</p> <p>Communicating with all stakeholders the results and strive to use tools and language tailored to each of them</p> <p>Obtain feedback (in an anonymous manner) from all participants (online form etc.)</p>

	<p>Final results / reports being used to add value (and be useful) to each stakeholder (decision-making input)</p> <p>Acknowledging contributions from stakeholders</p> <p>Establishing long-term processes that enable continuous feedback and adaptation of the representation.</p>
Generating mutual learning	
Context and purpose	<p>Mapping wide/appropriate range of existing local competencies and needs (e.g., via literature reviews, interviews, meetings)</p> <p>Recognizing different levels of prior knowledge and capacity to learn about key themes</p> <p>Collecting requests / views from all participant groups before defining the learning needs</p> <p>Learning about previous local experience with engagement and public participation</p> <p>Identifying who can teach whom what</p>
Pre-engagement	<p>Establish from the beginning that the CEI will be a place of mutual learning (not exchange)</p> <p>Creating heterogeneous work groups that are directed to consider diverse perspectives</p> <p>Embed the process in the local culture/networks with the aim of strengthening existing links and building relationships with community members</p> <p>Design mutual learning processes based on participant-identified needs</p> <p>Providing tangible examples of what is requested/involved in the mutual learning process</p>
On-the-day engagement	<p>Inclusive, accessible communication (language(s), avoiding jargon, pausing to check ideas have been clearly received)</p> <p>Communicate and engage respectfully and attentively (listen to experiences, collect knowledge)</p> <p>Promote bottom-up approach that draws in different inputs and points of view (though this may be more difficult with citizens)</p> <p>Openly set expectation that participants are the experts and encourage mutual learning</p> <p>Creating an environment where participants actively listen to others</p> <p>Creative engagement methods (role play, games)</p> <p>Carrying out the engagement activities in a context- and power-appropriate way e.g., bottom-up, equalized, exchange of views between participants</p> <p>Providing real-time feedback during the process</p>
Post-engagement	<p>Knowledge developed clearly communicated to participants and wider society (e.g. ask participants to proofread before wider publication) in context-appropriate format (e.g. using maps)</p>

	<p>Steering towards the development of open-access datasets/maps/platforms</p> <p>Providing tools/criteria to evaluate and demonstrate what the project/organization has learned through the mutual learning process</p> <p>Seek honest reflections from participants soon after the process completes</p> <p>Evaluate learning during the process with the participants</p>
Producing improved collaboration	
Context and purpose	<p>Examining existing or past collaboration practices with citizens to learn lessons from them</p> <p>Identifying and context-specific analysis of existing relations/conflicts between local citizens / representatives / decision makers and potential reasons behind lack of collaboration</p> <p>Build on existing social capital (networks, relationships, nodes etc.)</p> <p>Exploring local nuances and using these to tailor which/how external ideas and methods are used</p> <p>Trust building activities with to-be-engaged citizens</p> <p>Immersing the process and organizers in the local context</p>
Pre-engagement	<p>Purposeful selection: choosing citizens/participants with a clear idea of the final goal intended to be achieved from the event</p> <p>Going beyond existing networks to rely on context-representative group</p> <p>Going beyond engaging with the ‘usual suspects’ (i.e. citizens/participants that already participate in similar processes).</p> <p>Engage early with local participants and ask to use their networks</p> <p>Leverage existing networks (organizers’ and participants’)</p> <p>The process and its expected impacts are co-defined, effectively communicated and agreed with citizens</p> <p>Plan early, including any role for citizens, how the results will be communicated</p> <p>Specifically provide opportunities for citizens to impact planning or process decision making</p> <p>Determine participant’s capacity to contribute throughout the process and offer appropriate support to those who may need it</p> <p>Ensuring process ownership, making benefits to all citizens clear (to achieve buy in)</p> <p>Clearly communicating the benefits to participants of collaboration</p> <p>Transparency on the intention to favor collaboration among participants</p> <p>Participant attribute (co-) assessment: understand competencies, expertise and what they bring in</p>
On-the-day engagement	<p>Help citizens find synergies and common interests</p> <p>Show commitment and maintain a helpful and supporting approach</p> <p>Clear goals: e.g., understanding (on the part of the facilitator) of what is required by the working group</p>

	<p>Providing clear and concise informational material to work on</p> <p>Clearly and collectively define the role of each participant over the process</p> <p>Providing time for informal exchange among participants</p> <p>Adequate time provided for knowledge sharing with and between citizens</p> <p>A range of activities based on voluntary, multi-direction communication where participants recognize the value of collaborating (to them and the process overall)</p> <p>Deliberative process actively accounts for citizens' communication preferences / capacities</p> <p>Flexible agenda to be able to add in emerging topics</p>
<p>Post-engagement</p>	<p>Next steps (immediate and future) are clearly identified and communicated to citizens</p> <p>Clearly defined next steps</p> <p>Timely response to participants after the event</p> <p>Provide feedback at the end of the engagement event (e.g. material summarizing the next steps of the process)</p> <p>Including participants in next steps as appropriate</p> <p>Avoiding the "black hole": maintain contact with participants after the conclusion of the event and (if applicable) follow up with other initiatives</p> <p>Facilitate follow-on activities to maintain the relationships built (e.g. mailing list, exchanging contacts, initial next-steps meetings)</p> <p>Seek opportunities to create a longer-lasting community and further opportunities for collaboration</p> <p>Dedicating efforts to maintaining relationships after the end of the project</p> <p>Designing proper governance within the network which would allow self organization among stakeholders (e.g. mechanisms that would allow continuation of the local networks)</p> <p>Without forcing local collaborations if not requested</p> <p>With consideration of social groups and their representatives</p> <p>Seek consent to continue engagement beyond the end of the current project (e.g. with follow-up results or activities)</p> <p>Recognizing and leveraging external collaborations that stemmed from the process</p> <p>Ensuring participants feel "useful" and their collaboration is relevant (e.g. show how ideas and inputs are actually shaping the decisions)</p>

Appendix 3: Full Survey

The full survey questionnaire is provided in the table below:

Main theme	Categories
What stakeholder category best describes your organisation?	Academia or Research Institution
	Citizen collective (e.g. communities, social movements)
	Civil servants (e.g. government or agency employees)
	Politician (elected officials)
	Specialised Consultancy (e.g. experts in engagement, communication, event planning)
	Third sector institution (e.g. NGOs, philanthropic organisations)
	Other Private Sector Representatives
	Other
	Other (please specify):
How familiar are you with carrying out CEIs in general?	I have been involved in one or two;
	I am fairly experienced;
	I have lots of experience.
As a reminder, we are keen on specific experiences. Thus, please provide some general details of the initiative or project you will reflect on:	Project name
	Location
	Country
	Start (Month/Year)
	End (Month/Year or "Ongoing")
	Website (Project's own or other information source)
Please select the most appropriate climate change adaptation sector:	Adaptation (general)
	Agriculture
	Biodiversity
	Buildings
	Business and Industry
	Coastal areas
	Cultural Heritage
	Disaster risk reduction
	Energy
	Environment
	Financial
	Forestry
	Health
	ICT
	Land use planning
	Marine & fisheries
	Mountain areas
Tourism	
Transport	

	Urban
	Water management
	If more than one, please write the additional sector(s) below:
Please select the main environmental hazard the project focused on:	Climate Change in General (non-specific hazard)
	Extreme heat events
	Cold spells / snaps
	Frost
	Wildfires
	Warmer climate over time
	Colder climate over time
	Droughts
	Heavy rainfall events
	River floods
	Surface water (torrential, flash) floods
	Landslides (due to heavy rainfall)
	Wetter climate over time
	Drier climate over time
	Severe wind storms
	Tropical cyclones
	Sand and dust storms
	Windier climate over time
	Less windy climate over time
	Heavy snowfall and ice storms
	Hail
	Ice sheet melt, lake melt, and river ice melt
	Snow avalanches
	Freeze-thaw cycles
	Coastal floods
	Coastal erosion
	Sea-level rise
	Marine heatwaves
	Marine cold waves
	Warmer oceans over time
	Colder oceans over time
	Changes in ocean chemistry
	Fog
Lightning	
Air pollution-inducing weather	
Radiation at surface	
If more than one, please write the additional hazard(s) below:	
Project logistics:	How many separate meetings did the project involve?
	How many citizens were involved (please estimate if the actual number is unknown)?

	Could you provide an estimated cost for the initiative? If you do not have this information or prefer not to disclose it, please leave the box blank.
Alongside citizens, were any other societal groups involved as participants (i.e. did they contribute to the discussions or decision making)?	Open-Ended Response
Were any other societal groups involved in other roles? [Advisory; Communication; Expert; Funder; Implementer; Organiser; Other]	Citizen Collectives (e.g. communities, social movements)
	Third Sector Institutions (e.g. NGOs, philanthropic organisations)
	Civil servants (e.g. government or agency employees)
	Politicians (elected officials)
	Academics/researchers
	Specialised Consultancies (e.g. experts in engagement or event planning)
	Other Private Sector Representatives
Other - Other	
What was the specific goal of the initiative (e.g., part of a policy process, public budgeting, etc.)	Open-ended response
Motivation 1:	Open-ended response
Motivation 2:	Open-ended response
Motivation 3:	Open-ended response
Were there any specific reasons that a CEI was chosen? (e.g. legal requirement, political commitment, part of a series of initiatives, available human/financial resources, proof of concept, research-project related)	Open-ended response
Which of the following most closely corresponds to the type of initiative?	Assembly
	Citizen science
	Civic body/committee
	Climathon
	Conversation cafés
	Council
	Dialogues
	Forums/forum theatres
	Jury
	Panel
	Public budgeting
	Public meeting
	Roundtables
Other (please specify)	
Were any target citizen groups identified?	Yes
	No
	If yes: please can you explain how the target citizen groups were identified, including why the group were chosen and who was in charge of identifying them?

Please can you tell us about the measures used to invite participants to the initiative? For example, can you provide details on:	What was done (e.g., sampling strategy, communication, intermediaries)
	Who was responsible for conducting these measures?
	How effective were these methods at getting citizens to begin attending the CEI?
	Would you do anything different if you carried out a similar exercise in the future?
Despite these efforts, were there any factors beyond the control of the CEI organisers that hindered (or helped) bring people to the CEI?	Open-Ended Response
Recalling the first motivation you identified in Q11 ({{ Q11 }}), can you provide details on:	What was done during the CEI in support of this motivation (e.g...was any background material provided, what engagement method(s) was chosen, were participants compensated for their time or was childcare available)?
	Who was responsible for what?
	Overall, how well was the motivation achieved, and how effective were these methods in this?
	Would you do anything different if it were necessary to do a similar exercise in the future?
Recalling the second motivation you identified in Q12 ({{ Q12 }}), can you provide details on:	What was done during the CEI in support of this motivation (e.g...was any background material provided, what engagement method(s) was chosen, were participants compensated for their time or was childcare available)?
	Who was responsible for what?
	Overall, how well was the motivation achieved, and how effective were these methods in this?
	Would you do anything different if it were necessary to do a similar exercise in the future?
Recalling the third motivation you identified in Q13 ({{ Q13 }}), can you provide details on:	What was done during the CEI in support of this motivation (e.g...was any background material provided, what engagement method(s) was chosen, were participants compensated for their time or was childcare available)?
	Who was responsible for what?
	Overall, how well was the motivation achieved, and how effective were these methods in this?
	Would you do anything different if it were necessary to do a similar exercise in the future?
Were citizens involved in the design of the engagement process?	Yes
	No
	If Yes, can you provide details or what happened and how citizens contributed?
Can you tell us how decisions were taken during the initiative and whether citizens were involved (e.g. was there a public vote, was there consensus, were decisions taken by citizen representatives?) We are particularly interested in any decisions related to the specific goal of the initiative ({{ Q8 }}).	Open-Ended Response
Regarding the outputs and outcomes of the CEI:	What results were generated?
	What next steps were identified?
	Who was responsible for carrying these out?

	(How) were the results and next steps communicated to participants?
	(How) were the results and next steps communicated to the broader public?
	How effective were the results and next steps in meeting the original objectives?
	Would you do anything different if it were necessary to do a similar exercise in the future?
Was an evaluation of the CEI carried out? Yes/No	Yes
	No
	If yes, can you provide details on: - What happened (e.g. was there a survey, were participants interviewed) - Who carried out the evaluation? - Were the findings of the evaluation made available? - Did the findings suggest the CEI had achieved its goals and satisfied the motivations? - Did the evaluation include suggestions for doing things differently next time? - Would you do anything different for a future evaluation?
Did the CEI have any effects beyond the direct outputs/outcomes mentioned above (e.g. are CEIs now normalised, or did a new community group form)?	Open-Ended Response
Thinking back over your responses for this specific CEI, do you think they also apply to any other types of CEIs or to CEIs in general? Other examples of CEIs include assemblies; panels; conversation cafés; roundtables; councils; forums/forum theatres; juries; dialogues etc.	Open-Ended Response
Is there anything else you would like to add?	Open-Ended Response
How your answers contribute to research and peer learning: We would like to send you the results of the survey and invite you to an online peer-learning workshop to validate the conclusions we obtain. Could you please select your preferences?	I would like to receive the results of the study and be invited to the peer-learning workshop
	I would like to only receive the results of the study
	I would like to opt-out of all forms of further communication
	If you selected the first or second options, please add your email here:

Appendix 4: Review of methodologies

Document	European Commission. (2024). <i>Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/736 of 1 March 2024 on a Code of Practice on citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation</i> . Official Journal of the European Union, L 185, 1–10.
Institution	European Commission
Available at	EUR-Lex - 32024H0736 - EN - EUR-Lex https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32024H0736
What's in?	The aim of the Code of practice on citizen engagement for knowledge valorisation is to provide guidance and relevant tools for actors involved in research and innovation (R&I). It understands “knowledge valorisation” as the process of creating social and economic value from knowledge by linking different areas and sectors and by transforming data, know-how and research results into sustainable products, services, solutions and knowledge-based policies that benefit society.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recommendations for a code of practice

Summary of best practices

BUILDING AN ENABLING ENVIRONMENT FOR SUSTAINABLE CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT

2.1. Adopt an engagement strategy for value creation:

- Define engagement objectives and incentives.
- Explain how citizen engagement adds societal value.
- Identify short-, mid-, and long-term impact pathways.
- Develop a roadmap to ensure engagement benefits society and the economy.
- Include monitoring and evaluation frameworks for societal and economic impact.

2.2. Build capacity and create synergies:

- Train staff to improve participatory practices.
- Develop expertise in public administrations for co-creation and engagement.
- Identify and build synergies with other initiatives and private companies.
- Continuously explore relevant policies and strategies.

2.3. Adopt cross-sector collaboration and manage intellectual assets:

- Promote cross-sector collaboration to create transdisciplinary initiatives.
- Address intellectual assets, recognizing all contributions.
- Use open access when appropriate and respect privacy and ethics.

2.4. Ensure inclusion, diversity, and gender equality:

- Adapt engagement strategies to reach all groups, including marginalized people.
- Recognize varying engagement capacities among citizens.
- Build interdisciplinary teams and include specialized experts when needed.

2.5. Promote replication and scalability:

- Support adaptable frameworks, toolkits, and guidelines.
- Share best practices and involve intermediaries for replication.
- Use platforms connecting R&I stakeholders and document best practices.

2.6. Recognize participants' time and effort:

- Develop incentives, such as recognition and awards.
- Integrate citizen engagement contributions into performance evaluations.

2.7. Increase awareness of knowledge valorisation benefits:

- Organize public awareness initiatives involving key stakeholders.
- Run awareness campaigns and training within organizations.
- Engage citizens through campaigns, assemblies, and online platforms.

2.8. Adopt a clear evaluation framework for citizen engagement:

- Define indicators to evaluate engagement efficacy.
- Look beyond outputs to assess outcomes and impact.
- Focus on outreach, participation, and value creation.

MANAGING CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT FOR KNOWLEDGE VALORISATION

3.1. Clarify partner incentives and expectations:

- Define incentives for citizens, researchers, industry, and policymakers.
- Ensure incentives are ethically aligned and culturally sensitive.
- Set expectations collaboratively and ensure flexibility.

3.2. Maintain momentum throughout the engagement:

- Foster transparency and trust.
- Keep an open, accessible exchange of ideas.
- Provide citizens with access to information and necessary training.

3.3. Choose suitable methods and tools:

- Match methods to objectives, target groups, and resources.
- Use best practices and share knowledge gained from engagement actions.

3.4. Develop a communication strategy:

- Provide clear communication materials and updates.
- Maintain transparent messages, using science communicators if possible.
- Enable feedback throughout and promote stories and successes publicly.

3.5. Leverage digital technologies:

- Use human-centric, sustainable digital tools.
- Train citizens on digital platforms to increase engagement.
- Combine digital with traditional methods to boost inclusiveness.

Document	MIP4ADAPT (2023). <i>Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Adaptation: A DIY Manual</i> . Manual.
Available at	https://climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/mission/solutions/citizen-engagement-manual
Institution	MIP4Adapt
What's in?	The aim of the Manual for Stakeholder and Citizen Engagement in Climate Adaptation is to guide regional/local authorities on engaging stakeholders and citizens in adaptation planning. It highlights communicate, engage, connect, enable as four key elements. The manual also addresses the importance of engagement, highlighting that public participation improves awareness and commitment, making plans salient, credible, legitimate, and understood.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Examples of participatory activities with links to e.g., handbooks and webinars for each of the steps (see “Summary of best practices”) • Tools and links for participatory methodologies: stakeholder mapping, citizen science, climate assemblies, participatory budgeting, social network analysis. • Examples of projects which used participatory approaches

Summary of best practices

Step 1: Preparing the Ground

1. **Define Objectives:** Clarify why and who to engage, ensuring alignment of interests and clear stakeholder roles.
2. **Mapping Stakeholders:** Identify and categorize stakeholders using tools like influence-interest matrices and social network analysis.
3. **Create a Mobilization Strategy:** Outline activities and resources needed for sustained engagement and manage expectations.
4. **Plan Communication:** Tailor messages for effective communication, with support from experts.

Step 2: Assess Risks and Vulnerabilities

- **Engage to Validate Findings:** Use focus groups and workshops to gain input on vulnerabilities, adaptive capacities, and exposure.
- **Gather Qualitative Data:** Understand stakeholders’ perceptions, concerns, and motivations, using participatory methods like visioning or mapping.

Step 3: Identify Adaptation Options

- **Stakeholder and Citizen Input:** Validate adaptation options through targeted workshops or cross-sectoral discussions, with a focus on synergies.

Step 4: Assess and Prioritize Options

- **Decision Support:** Apply criteria for prioritization through workshops and citizens’ input to create actionable adaptation options.

Step 5: Implementing the Plan

- **Promote Participation:** Involve stakeholders and citizens in developing policies and identifying funding. Use deliberative processes like Community Dialogues for stronger engagement.
- **Encourage Community Support:** Engage stakeholders in co-decision processes like green participatory budgeting for better local climate solutions.

Step 6: Monitor and Evaluate

- **Regular Review:** Monitor progress, involve citizens in tracking adaptation actions, and promote accountability.
- **Citizen Science:** Use citizen science for ongoing input, adapting plans based on real-time feedback and ensuring commitment.

Document	Jaubin, J. (ED.) et al. (2021). <i>Citizen Engagement Solution Booklet</i> . EU Smart Cities Information System. European Commission. P. 1-49.
Institution	European Commission – Smart Cities Marketplace
Available at	https://smart-cities-marketplace.ec.europa.eu/insights/solutions/solution-booklet-citizen-engagement
What's in?	The aim of the Citizen Engagement Solution Booklet is to provide cities with resources for engaging citizens such as recommendations, but also adds the reasons behind opting for citizen engagement in finding solutions for cities.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of citizen engagement and some examples found in the EU • CityxChange project resources: frameworks, tools and examples • SET Social Engagement Toolkit • Catalogue of Tools for Citizen Engagement and Participation

Summary of best practices

Getting Started

1. **Purpose:** Define clear engagement goals. Use models like the IRIS Citizen Engagement Ladder for structuring levels of citizen influence.
2. **Budget:** Allocate sufficient resources; incorporate engagement into core municipal budgets for sustainability.
3. **Time:** Plan enough time for meaningful participation.
4. **Stakeholder Types:** Map diverse stakeholders, considering social factors (age, migration, disability).
5. **Culture:** Tailor approaches to community culture; use local champions to promote engagement.
6. **Problem Type and Size:** Adjust approaches based on problem complexity (e.g., small projects vs. city-wide policies).
7. **Offline vs. Online:** Balance online tools with face-to-face engagement in familiar, accessible locations.
8. **Decision Phase:** Engage early to shape solutions collaboratively.
9. **Experience:** Build on past engagement efforts; seek external expertise if needed.

Citizen Engagement in Action

1. **Context Understanding:** Explore all aspects of the problem; consider cultural, economic, and social factors.
2. **Purpose Setting:** Clearly define goals and expectations with citizens to align city efforts.
3. **Capacity Building:** Equip staff and citizens with knowledge and skills for effective engagement; use participatory tools like games.
4. **Diverse Stakeholder Inclusion:** Tailor communication to stakeholder needs; apply segmentation to address specific groups.
5. **Activities, Tools, and Infrastructure:** Use design thinking, living labs, and physical spaces to support ongoing engagement.
6. **Open Data:** Share data to increase transparency and encourage informed participation.
7. **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Set measurable KPIs from the start; use both quantitative and qualitative assessments.
8. **Privacy:** Follow GDPR, minimize data use, and prioritize transparency to build citizen trust.

General Lessons Learned

1. **Knowledge and Capacity Building:** Invest in knowledge sharing and collaboration tools.
2. **Collaborative Governance:** Integrate engagement into broader strategic planning.
3. **From Buzzword to Reality:** Embed citizen engagement into municipal practices for real impact.
4. **Timely Engagement:** Start early in decision processes to maximize influence.
5. **Building Trust:** Use local ambassadors and be transparent about processes and results.
6. **Shifting Paradigms:** Move from central meetings to engaging citizens in their own spaces.
7. **Utilize Existing Resources:** Build on current engagement efforts and active community members.

Document	Evaeus, B. (ED.) (2021). <i>Transforming cities together: a public engagement guide for cities</i> . Guide. CIVOCRACY/WWF. P. 1-61.
Available at	https://wwf.panda.org/projects/one_planet_cities/what_we_do/public_engagement_guide_for_cities/
Institution	WWF
What's in?	The aim of the guide on Transforming cities together: a public engagement guide for cities is to provide tools for cities and city planners to increase public engagement.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 factors for success (see ‘Summary of best practices’) • Examples from WWF’s One Planet City Challenge partners • Questions to consider when planning a public engagement campaign

Summary of best practices

Five Core Principles for Effective Public Engagement

1. **Define Goals and Expectations:**
 - Clarify project goals for internal alignment and to clearly communicate to citizens.
 - Set specific, measurable goals to engage citizens meaningfully and be prepared to adjust based on their feedback.
2. **Be Transparent:**
 - Building trust requires transparency; share decisions, processes, and challenges openly.
 - Keep citizens updated throughout the project lifecycle and acknowledge both successes and setbacks.
3. **Be Inclusive:**
 - Make active efforts to engage marginalized voices, adapting communication strategies to reach diverse groups.
 - Work with trusted local organizations to connect with underrepresented communities.
4. **Show Commitment:**
 - Avoid superficial engagement; ensure that citizen feedback is considered in decision-making and follow through on it.
 - Build long-term relationships by consistently engaging citizens beyond one-off projects, fostering trust over time.
5. **Trust Your Citizens:**
 - Value citizens’ input, including critical feedback, as it can provide valuable insights and help improve projects.
 - Encourage citizens to take an active role, promoting a sense of ownership and shared responsibility for community outcomes.

Key core questions

The answers to these questions will help identify: • Necessary resources • Key target audiences • Useful data collection • Potential partners

- What are your goals?
- What are your city’s demographics?
- Who have you planned to engage with?
 - Who are the experts? Who will be impacted? Who has a vested interest in the project area and subject? Which groups are already advocates and activists for

your goals? Are there some diverse opinions or voices that you have not heard from in the past? Who is local to your project area? Are there any established groups or institutions that fall into the above categories?

- Where do people in your city get their information?
- What messaging will you use? How do different communication styles impact who you reach?
- Who are potential (internal and external) partners you can work with in engaging the public?
- At what stage in planning are you?
- What resources do you have at your disposal?
- What level of engagement are you aiming for?

Document	Stec, S., Abat, A., Hafen, F., Niestroy, I., & Sperrin, Á. (2020). <i>Frameworks for citizen engagement in the European Green Deal: The REAL DEAL handbook</i> . European Environmental Bureau (EEB). https://www.realdeal.eu/handbook
Available at	https://www.realdeal.eu/handbook
Institution	European Environmental Bureau (EEB) – REALDEAL project
What's in?	“The REAL DEAL Handbook gives a snapshot of the existing legal and institutional frameworks for citizen engagement in relation to the EGD. It aims to provide a clear understanding of the legal, institutional and policy background for citizen engagement as a foundation for considering possible forms, formats, methods and tools for participation to use in the future. The Handbook examines two main types of citizen engagement. The first is participatory style engagement, which fulfils legal minimum requirements for policy makers to engage the public. Europe’s quarter-century experience with the Aarhus Convention is invaluable in this regard. The second type explores innovative forms of engagement based on consultative and deliberative mechanisms such as citizen assemblies.”
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of the regulatory framework for citizen engagement within EU legislation and linkages to international agreements (European Green Deal, Agenda 2030, Rio principles), as well as in Non-EU Member States • Practices for consultative and deliberative mechanisms • See Table 5 Types of deliberative democratic processes, and accompanying factsheets in the following resource (for the methods: planning cells, focus groups, citizens’ assemblies, participatory modelling, 21st Century Town Meeting®, Delphi Method, Public Participation Network, Roundtable, Salon Method, Analytic Deliberative Process, Public Hearing and Experts Panel. See: https://www.realdeal.eu/221031_deliverable_1_2

Summary of best practices

Chapter 6. Recommendations for Institutionalizing Citizen Engagement in the EGD

1. **REAL DEAL Criteria for Citizen Engagement:**
 - **Address Power Imbalances:** Empower marginalized groups and recognize power dynamics in policymaking.
 - **Ensure Inclusiveness:** Include all citizens, especially marginalized and indigenous groups, in environmental discussions.
 - **Protect Nature:** Acknowledge the moral value of non-human entities in policies.
 - **Support Grassroots Activism:** Integrate environmental activist insights and grassroots efforts into policymaking.
 - **Promote Green Economic Transition:** Encourage active citizen participation beyond consumption, fostering well-being over growth.
2. **Outcome and Process Criteria for Engagement:**
 - **Outcomes:**
 - Enhance policy legitimacy and public support.
 - Foster citizen empowerment and sustainability awareness.
 - **Process:**
 - Ensure participation is fair, inclusive, cost-effective, and connected to policy from the outset.
3. **Structuring Recommendations for Engagement:**
 - Strengthen the **Aarhus Framework** for transparency and access to justice.

- Address gaps in implementation, such as **insufficient resources, training, and inter-organizational cooperation**.
- Improve participatory literacy and capacity in civil society organizations.
- 4. **Safeguards for Potential Engagement Risks:**
 - **Demographic Representation:** Ensure inclusivity by addressing intersectional barriers like gender, race, and socioeconomic status.
 - **Accessibility:** Make processes accessible to diverse groups, with flexible scheduling, remuneration, and support like childcare.
 - **Safe Spaces:** Create respectful and neutral discussion environments with skilled facilitation to prevent discrimination.
 - **Institutional Commitment:** Dedicate adequate resources and time to citizen consultations, incorporate feedback, and address power imbalances for genuine engagement.

Document	WHO (2024). Citizen engagement in evidence-informed policy-making: a guide to mini-publics. Geneva: World Health Organization. Licence: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO. P. 1-106.
Available at	https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240081413
Institution	WHO
What's in?	The aim of this guide to mini-publics for the health sector is to offer a thorough set of steps to use mini-publics for evidence-informed policy-making. Despite not being climate change adaptation focused, the guidelines provided go very in-depth and could be applicable for adaptation issues.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overview of the 'what' and 'why' of mini-publics • A four-stage framework to organise mini-publics. Each stage has steps, and the document provides resources for conducting each step.

Summary of best practices

The proposed framework to organise mini-publics is divided into four steps.

Inception stage (1 to 6 months)

- Step 1. Assess the viability of a mini-public
- Step 2. Form a Project Team
- Step 3. Mobilize institutional support
- Step 4. Develop a wider Project Network
- Step 5. Stakeholder workshop for developing a shared understandings of issues
- Step 6. Map the institutional landscape and wider socio-political context
- Step 7. Decide on the type of mini-public
- Step 8. Decide on key principles to guide your practice
- Step 9. Generate a Project Brief

Preparation stage (2 months minimum)

- Step 1. Form the Stewarding Board
- Step 2. Define the task of the mini-public
- Step 3. Prepare a Communication Plan and Impact Strategy
- Step 4. Recruit participants for the mini-public
- Step 5. Provide support for participants
- Step 6. Prepare the research evidence
- Step 7. Consolidate the Action Plan

Deliberation stage (Between 1 and 14 days, spread over 1–12 months)

- Step 1. Prepare participants, speakers and observers
- Step 2. Explore the evidence through learning sessions
- Step 3. Deliberate and generate policy considerations
- Step 4. Draft the Minipublic Report

Influence stage (6 months minimum)

- Process 1. Promoting the influence of the Mini-public Report
- Process 2. Evaluating the mini-public
- Coda: developing, embedding and institutionalizing citizen engagement via mini-publics

Document	OECD (2022), OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes, OECD Public Governance Reviews, OECD Publishing, Paris, https://doi.org/10.1787/f765caf6-en . P. 1-94.
Available at	https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/oecd-guidelines-for-citizen-participation-processes_f765caf6-en.html
Institution	OECD
What's in?	As described in their website, “the OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes are intended for any public official or public institution interested in carrying out a citizen participation process. The guidelines describe ten steps for designing, planning, implementing and evaluating a citizen participation process, and discuss eight different methods for involving citizens: information and data, open meetings, public consultations, open innovation, citizen science, civic monitoring, participatory budgeting and representative deliberative processes.”.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition, the difference between citizen and stakeholder engagement, reasons for and myths about citizen engagement • Guidelines for planning, implementing, and evaluating • Citizen participation methods: comparing key characteristics (Table 2.3.) and case studies for each listed method • List of digital tools with comparisons • Guiding principles for citizen engagement and how to ensure them, as well as lists of resources for all the covered aspects in the guide

Summary of best practices

Official summary found on the website and in the executive summary of the guidelines (p. 10-11)

Ten-step path of planning and implementing a citizen participation process

Citizen participation processes should be organised only when there is room for meaningful citizen participation in the decision-making process. A ten-step path was developed to provide guidance along the way:

1. **Identifying the problem to solve and the moment for participation:** The first step when planning a citizen participation process is to identify if there is a genuine problem that the public can help solve. If there is, then the problem needs to be defined and framed as a question. Citizens can be actively involved in any of the stages or throughout the policy cycle: when identifying the issue, formulating policy, making decisions, implementing policy, or evaluating it.
2. **Defining the expected results:** A clear understanding of the expected outcomes or results of the participation process is needed to define the desired inputs or contributions from citizens and the impact they will have on the final decision.
3. **Identifying the relevant group of people to involve and recruiting participants:** Different types of groups can be involved in a participation process, such as a broad group of citizens from diverse backgrounds, a representative group of citizens, a particular community based on geography or other demographic characteristics, as well as stakeholders, ranging from non-governmental organisations to businesses or academia. Different strategies can be employed to recruit them – an open call, a closed call, or a civic lottery.
4. **Choosing the participation method:** Eight citizen participation methods and their characteristics are compared and described to help choose the most applicable one in a given situation:

information and communication, open meetings/town hall meetings, civic monitoring, public consultation, open innovation, citizen science, participatory budgeting, and representative deliberative processes.

5. **Choosing the right digital tools:** Digital tools can allow citizens and stakeholders to interact and submit their inputs in different ways. They should be chosen to facilitate the participation method. Policy makers should keep in mind the existing “digital divides”, plan for technical, human, and financial resources needed to deploy digital tools, and choose tools that are transparent and accountable. When possible, digital tools should be chosen alongside in-person methods.
6. **Communicating about the process:** Public communication can help at every step of the way – from recruiting citizens, to ensuring the transparency of the process, to extending the benefits of learning about a specific policy issue to the broader public. Constant, clear, and understandable communication that uses plain language is most effective.
7. **Implementing the participation process:** There are general considerations that concern the implementation of any participatory process: preparing an adequate timeline, identifying the needed resources, ensuring inclusion and accessibility, and considering a citizens’ journey through a participatory process.
8. **Using citizen input and providing feedback:** The inputs received as part of the participatory process should be given careful and respectful consideration and used as stipulated in the beginning – with clear justifications if any inputs or recommendations are not used or implemented. Communicating to participants about the status of their inputs and the ultimate outcome of their participation helps to close the feedback loop.
9. **Evaluating the participation process:** Through evaluation, the quality and neutrality of a participatory process can be measured and demonstrated to the broader public. Evaluation also creates an opportunity for learning by providing evidence and lessons for public authorities and practitioners about what went well, and what did not.
10. **Fostering a culture of participation:** A shift from ad hoc participation processes to a culture of participation can be supported by embedding institutionalised participation mechanisms, multiplying opportunities for citizens to exercise their democratic “muscles” beyond participation, and protecting a vibrant civic space.

Guiding principles for quality citizen participation processes

The methods of citizen participation outlined in these guidelines rely on principles of good practice to ensure their quality: **clarity and impact, commitment and accountability, transparency, inclusiveness and accessibility, integrity, privacy, information, resources, and evaluation.**

Document	Hörschelmann, K; Werner, A; Bogacki, M; Lazova, Y (2019) Taking Action for Urban Nature: Citizen Engagement Handbook, NATURVATION Guide.
Available at	https://networknature.eu/product/22724
Institution	European Commission (NATURVATION project)
What's in?	The aim of this handbook for citizen engagement related to urban nature is to “provide a hands-on resource that enables municipalities and civil society organisations to enhance existing and establish new processes of participatory governance for the implementation of nature-based solutions.”
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of methods and examples with key steps and measures, chances and opportunities and key issues to consider for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ municipalities: future workshop, round table, participatory planning workshop, citizen panel ○ civil society organisations: district forum, appreciative inquiry & public spirit workshop, district-based community work, environmental education ○ for promoting the inclusion of marginalised groups: advocacy planning, community organizing • List of links to resources for each of the proposed method

Summary of best practices

Best practices to be applied across all proposed citizen engagement methods:

- Invest plenty of time in relationship and trust building. This is time consuming but lays a sound foundation to build upon.
- Engage at eye level and value the skills and knowledge that people bring, using methods of engagement that are respectful and appreciative of different contributions. Be wary of biases in the organisers’ team. Spot and be aware of hierarchies and self-interested groups amongst participants.
- Offer non-conditional opportunities to participate and ensure continued, ongoing support.
- Accept and be prepared for fluctuating levels of engagement.
- Have projects and interventions overseen by a combination of professionals and volunteers from different sectors.
- Get trained in conflict management and counteract the marginalisation of dissenting voices
- Mix social groups rather than isolating the disadvantaged and most vulnerable, while keeping in mind cultural differences.
- Provide and/or offer support with access to funding (private, public and crowd funded) and comprehensive information, including legal expertise.
- Secure long-term access to communal spaces and publicly owned land.
- Provide opportunities for hands-on participation and direct engagement, e.g. in green space development and maintenance or via plant donation and adoption schemes.

Document	African Union Development Agency - NEPAD. (n.d.). African Union handbook on citizen engagement. NEPAD. P. 1-56.
Available at	https://www.nepad.org/publication/african-union-handbook-citizen-engagement
Institution	NEPAD
What's in?	The aim of this handbook on citizen engagement is to “support the African Union Commission, Regional Economic Communities (RECs), Member States and stakeholders in conducting citizen engagement processes in a systematic and productive way. It builds on ongoing approaches to citizen engagement and aims at helping users to better understand specific approaches to citizen engagement and to guide them through the practical steps they can take to improve citizen engagement.
Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part 1: Chapter 1-5 focuses on the conceptual aspects of the handbook, covering policies, frameworks and preconditions for citizen engagement • Part 2: Chapter 6-8 focuses on the approaches to Citizen Engagement, starting with: informing, consultation, collaboration, citizen feedback, citizen-led monitoring and citizen engagement capacity monitoring. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What is it; Why is it important; Methods; Outcomes and indicators for successful implementation.

Summary of best practices

Best practices for citizen engagement – capacity building

1. Definition and Importance:

- **Purpose:** Develop citizens' skills for active participation, ensuring they have the necessary abilities to contribute meaningfully.
- **Three Levels of Capacity:**
 - **Enabling Environment:** Social systems, laws, and norms that frame engagement.
 - **Organizational Capacity:** Internal structures and policies within organizations supporting engagement.
 - **Individual Capacity:** Personal skills, knowledge, and experiences gained formally or informally.

2. Why Capacity Development is Vital:

- **Long-Term Transformation:** For Agenda 2063, developing citizens’ capacities is essential for sustainable community development, shifting mindsets, and promoting self-driven change.
- **Local Resources and Ownership:** Emphasizes using community resources and citizen knowledge to build sustainable change, complementing rather than replacing local capacities.
- **Promotes Inclusion:** Encourages partnerships that prioritize local knowledge, address power imbalances, and empower marginalized groups.

3. Methods for Capacity Development:

- **Clustering:** Networking organizations within a sector to increase collective strength and facilitate collaborative innovation.

- **Networking Events/Exposure Visits:** Facilitating knowledge-sharing events and visits to learn from successful peer organizations, fostering shared understanding and growth.
- **Citizen Resource Hubs:** Establishing online or physical platforms for information sharing, training resources, and collaborative tools to support knowledge exchange.
- **Citizen Literacy Campaigns/Workshops:** Providing targeted workshops and boot camps for skill development, ranging from single-day skill-focused events to comprehensive, multi-day sessions.

Table 6: Indicators of citizen engagement capacity development

Citizen capacity is built to improve citizen engagement	
Variable	Indicator
Capacity to act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ability to make choices ▪ Member’s ability to implement choices and move forward strategically ▪ Resources available to perform ▪ Enabling environment ▪ Strength of leadership ▪ Clarity of mandate
Capacity to achieve results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ability to achieve outputs and outcomes in line with an Organisation’s vision and mission ▪ Effective performance management of programs by Organisations
Capacity to relate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ability to be a part of the system of actors ▪ Ability to leverage resources and gain legitimacy among citizens ▪ Ability to enter into informal or formal alliances with other actors and citizen groups
Capacity to adapt	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ability to react to change productively and self-renew through adopting new ideas ▪ Ability to balance stability with adaptation to new conditions ▪ Evidence of resourcefulness of Organisations and citizens ▪ Evidence of resilience of Organisations and citizens ▪ Evidence of imagination of Organisations and citizens

Document	EIT-Climate KIC (accessed October 2024). <i>The Climathon playbook</i> . EIT-Climate KIC. Online resource.
Available at	https://climathon.climate-kic.org/organiser-toolkit/
Institution	EIT-Climate KIC
What's in?	The aim of this playbook is to support the organisation of 'Climathons'. A Climathon is defined as "an event where people come together to understand their local climate challenges and develop ideas for a net-zero carbon society. The focus is on unique ideas more than feasibility."
Resources	<p>Online handbook with several resources related to climathons:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The vision and goals of a climathon, as well as definitions with a dictionary • Getting started: defining the long-term impact (see https://www.climate-kic.org/who-we-are/making-an-impact/) • Fundraising strategies and creating a challenge • Organising and promoting a climathon (see 'Summary of best practices') with linked resources, follow-up and renewal • Resource library and Q&A

Summary of best practices

Best practices

- **Starting with the end-goal in mind:** defining the long-term impact, which includes the steps of identifying the goals, determining the target audience, assessing the impact, implementing and monitoring a plan and evaluating and adjusting.

Key Steps for Organizing a Climathon

- **Engaging Your City:** Involve local authorities by highlighting benefits, keeping them updated on progress.
- **Building Your Team:** Form a diverse team with clear roles like lead organizer, partnerships, communications, event, and volunteer leads. Communicate and structure regularly.
- **Involving Coaches, Experts, and Jury:** Early recruitment of experts, coaches, and jury members is crucial; seek partnerships that align with the Climathon's goals.
- **Recruiting Participants:** Engage diverse groups through local networks and online platforms, prepare for no-shows by over-registering, and consider pre-screening or refundable fees.
- **Finding a Venue:** Choose a space (physical or virtual) that meets participant needs, with internet, seating, and accessibility. For virtual, choose an engaging platform.
- **Designing the Program:**
 - **Program Length:** Typically 12-48 hours.
 - **Kick-Off:** Set an exciting tone, introduce goals, and share Climathon's impact.
 - **Challenge Understanding:** Encourage exploration of the local climate issue, using tools like the Iceberg Canvas.
 - **Team Building:** Organize teams based on skills and preferences; aim for diverse, manageable team sizes.
 - **Brainstorm and Prototype:** Use tools like the Iceberg Canvas to brainstorm, validate, and refine ideas with expert input.
 - **Energizers:** Include activities to re-energize participants.

- **Presentations:** End with team presentations to a jury for feedback and potential awards.
- **Networking:** Allow time for connections throughout the event.
- **Speakers:** Prepare speakers with event goals and ensure their message aligns with the challenge.
- **Awards:** Offer impactful prizes beyond money, like coaching or workspace, and announce awards in advance to boost participation.
- **Walking the Talk:** Model sustainable practices by providing vegetarian food, minimizing waste, promoting recycling, and offering sustainable awards. Consider virtual options to reduce the event's footprint.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Actions under grant agreement No 101093921